

RIGA TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY
Faculty of Engineering Economics and Management

HAMEED AFLICK, AJMAL KHAN

**Assessing the Influence of Foreign Direct Investments on
Market Valuation of Publicly Listed Indian Companies**

Master Thesis

Scientific Supervisor
RTU Asoc, Professor

Dr. Ilze, Sporge

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Anotācija

Ajmal Khan, HA. Ārvalstu tiešo investīciju ietekmes uz Indijas publisko uzņēmumu tirgus vērtību novērtējums: Maģistra darbs/ Ajmal Khan, HA., Ilze Sporge, Dr. (2025) Rīga: RTU IEVF akadēmiskā maģistra studiju programma "Uzņēmējdarbības finanses", 82 lpp.

Maģistra darbs ir uzrakstīts angļu valodā, sastāv no ievada, teorētiskā pamatojuma, pētījuma metodoloģijas, empīriskās daļas, secinājumiem un ieteikumiem. Darba apjoms ir 82 lappuses, tajā iekļauti 37 attēli, 4 tabulas, 10 formulas. Izmantotās literatūras un avotu saraksts - 79 avoti angļu valodā, darbam pievienoti pielikumi..

Pētījuma mērķis ir novērtēt ārvalstu tiešo investīciju (ĀTI) ietekmi uz izvēlētu publiski kotētu Indijas uzņēmumu tirgus vērtību, koncentrējoties uz ĀTI un finanšu darbības rādītāju savstarpējās saistības identificēšanu.

Pirmajā darba daļā satur pētījuma teorētisko ietvaru, kurā ir sniegts pārskats par faktoriem, kas ietekmē ārvalstu tiešo investīciju pieplūdumu, un ārvalstu tiešo investīciju panākumi tiek mērīti ar teoriju palīdzību..

Otrajā darba daļā ietver pētījuma metodoloģiju, kas ietver pētījuma dizainu, 40 uzņēmumu datu vākšana ietver divus dažādus modeļus, piemēram, regresijas modeli un investīciju uztveres modeli.

Trešajā darba daļā ietver pētījuma empīrisko daļu, kas ietver aprakstošās statistikas analīzi, korelācijas analīzi, izmantojot siltuma kartes, kā arī divus modeļus ar hipotēžu pārbaudi.

Nozīmīgākie rezultāti:

Pētījums apstiprina, ka ĀTI statistiski pozitīvi ietekmē uzņēmuma vērtību. Optimālais regresijas modelis pēc noviržu novēršanas un heteroskedastiskuma korekcijas uzrādīja pozitīvu ĀTI koeficientu 0,4442 un augstāko nozīmīgo P vērtību 0,0000038, kas norāda, ka ĀTI tieši veicina augstāku tirgus vērtību.

Atslēgas vārdi: ĀTI, kapitāla pieplūdums, ekonomikas izaugsme, ārvalstu kapitāla novērtējums, inovācijas, nodarbinātības pieaugums, sociālā un vides labklājība, ienākošie ĀTI, kapitāla konta politika

Annotation

Ajmal Khan, HA. Assessing the Influence of Foreign Direct Investments on Market Valuation of Publicly Listed Indian Companies: Master Thesis/ Ajmal Khan, HA., Ilze Sporge, Dr. (2025) Riga: RTU FEEM academic master study program "Business Finances", 82p.

The Master thesis consists of an introduction, theoretical framework, Research methodology, empirical part, conclusions, and recommendations. The scope of the Thesis is to assess the impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on the market valuation of selected publicly listed Indian companies, focusing on identifying the relationship between FDI and financial performance indicators. The total number of pages is 82, including 37 figures, 4 tables, and 10 formulas and bibliography 79 sources in English. The Thesis is written in English language.

The aim of the research is to assess the impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on the market valuation of selected publicly listed Indian companies, focusing on identifying the relationship between FDI and financial performance indicators.

Part 1 of the Master thesis contains the Theoretical framework of the research which explained overview of the factor influencing FDI inflows and success of FDI is measured with theories.

Part 2 of the Master thesis contains the research methodology which contains research design, data collection of 40 companies includes two different models such as Regression model and Investment Perception model.

Part 3 of the Master thesis contains the empirical part of the research which contains descriptive statistics analysis, correlation analysis with use of heat maps along with two models with testing of hypothesis.

The most important conclusions and recommendations resulting from the research:

The study confirms that FDI has a statistical and a positive impact on the enterprise value the optimal regression model after removing the outliers and correcting for heteroscedasticity showed a positive coefficient of FDI 0.4442 and with the highest significant P value of 0.0000038 indicating that FDI directly contributes the higher market valuation.

Keywords: FDI, Capital Inflows, Economic Growth, Foreign Equity Valuations, Innovations, Employment Growth, Social and Environmental Welfare, Inward FDI, Capital Account Policies.

Table of Contents

Introduction	5
1. Theoretical framework of the research.....	9
1.1 Modigliani and Miller's theory.....	9
1.2 The Financial Liberalization Hypothesis and its Role in Enhancing FDI Efficiency ...	12
1.3 Ohlson Valuation Model.....	14
1.4 Regulatory Framework and Factors Influencing FDI Inflows in Indian States.....	16
1.5 Literature review.....	20
2 Methodology of the research	32
2.1 Data Preparation and Cleaning	42
2.2 Regression model.....	46
3 Empirical part of the research.....	48
3.1 Regression model analysis.....	59
Conclusions and proposals	72
List of references	77

Introduction

Foreign direct investment, FDI has become a much required pillar of economic development, particularly in growing markets, where capital constraints, technology gaps and managerial inefficiencies often affects the substantial growth. When the globalization increases the developing countries like India is highly relied on FDI to increase industrial productivity, enhance infrastructure and stimulate employment generation. by drawing foreign investments, these economies gain access for advanced technology, global business enterprise, and improved government framework, and all of which contributes to the long-term economic stability and market competitiveness (Upadhyay, 2016). India being a rapidly evolving economy its main aim is to involve largely in the global marketplace. To help this foreign direct investment represents a strategy lifeline for the growth of domestic markets in India. India post liberation of economy has been heavily active in attracting foreign investment to help to fuel its industrial growth, develop its infrastructure and create more employment opportunities. (Sanyal et al., 2023) India's economic liberation in 1991 was a turning point in its approach to foreign investment, the government introduced various policies and reforms, which reduces restriction on foreign ownership and using regulatory barriers to create more investor, friendly environment so as a result, India has become one of the most attractive destination for FDI in the middle of emerging economies. As a result of this the Indian publicly listed company have transformed with the help of leveraging FDI to scale its operations and to compete in the global market. Foreign investors, which ranks from multinational corporations to institutional investors, has played a critical role in growth of various sectors, which includes technology manufacturing, pharmaceutical and financial services so the steady inflow of FDI has transformed Indian businesses by enabling them to expand operations, adopt international's best practices and competed in global market workforce (Bhat, 2024).

One of the most significant impact of FDI is the effect on the evaluation of public companies. Market valuation, which is commonly measured by market capitalization, which the total value of the company's outstanding shares will serve as a key indicator for the firm's financial health, investors confidence and for long-term growth. (Ji, 2024) Market valuation rather than being just a numerical indicator it symbolises the collective perception of the stakeholders, strategy alignment and the company's adaptability. It also helps us to understand how the company communicates its vision to market, aligning with the micro economic trends

and also addressing competitive challenges. For Indian firms particularly those from the sectors where global competition is heavy achieving and sustaining the market position and improving market valuation of the company is a big process which a company needs to have operational resilience and strategic foresight. While FDI directly contributes to capital infusion, but its influence extends beyond the financial investment. The foreign investors introduced highest standard of governance, advanced operational strategies and technological innovation, which hence the overall performance and the credibility of the firm they invest in. These improvements can lead to the increased investor trust, minimal financial risk and enhance the stock performance (Baker et al., 2004).

Companies make use of market valuation to assist their competent position and identify the key areas for improvement, which is important for long-term sustainability. So by understanding their market valuation, the firm can analyze industry, trends, benchmark against competitor and adjustments to hence the financial health of the firm (Slade, 2011). Valuation methods, such as present value cash flow DCF and relative valuation which provides insights about a company, market perception and the natural worth. These methods help firms to understand their value drivers which includes revenue, growth, profitability and risk factors. Similarly incorporating, social, and environmental factors into valuation strategy ensure alignment with sustainable business practices and investor expectation. By leveraging the evaluation inside business, scan, optimize capital allocation, improve efficiency of operations, and create long-term shareholder value.

Despite of the all apparent benefits, the relationship between FDI and the market valuation is complex and influenced by various factors. Macroeconomics, conditions, industry, specific trends, corporate governance, and structure and global financial market fluctuations plays a crucial role in determining how FDI affects the stock prices and shareholder value (Baker et al., 2008). Apart from that, while some company experience significant growth in market valuation due to foreign investment, others may face challenges related to ownership, dilution, strategic misalignment or regulatory constraints. So these variations require a deeper examination of the underlying mechanism through which influences the public traded firms in India.

The topicality of the study is grounded in the growing reliance of emerging economies like India on foreign direct investment as a driver of economic expansion, technological development and market competitiveness. With India becoming one of the top destinations for global capital inflow it is important to understand how FDI influence the market value of public listed companies, and it is also critical for investors, policy makers and corporate strategist.

The aim of the research is to assess the impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) on the market valuation of selected publicly listed Indian companies, focusing on identifying the relationship between FDI and financial performance indicators.

The research objectives are :

- To evaluate the influence of FDI on the enterprise value of selected publicly listed Indian companies.
- To analyze the relationship between FDI and financial performance indicators such as profitability, liquidity, and efficiency.
- To critically review existing literature on the role of FDI in enhancing the financial performance and market valuation of firms.
- To determine whether companies with FDI perform better in terms of market valuation compared to companies without FDI.

Following research question are formulated:

1. What is the impact of FDI on the market valuation of selected Indian listed companies?
2. How does FDI influence financial performance indicators such as profitability, liquidity, and efficiency?
3. Does the presence of FDI lead to a significant difference in the enterprise value of companies compared to those without FDI?

Based on the research question the following hypothesis is formulated :

H1: Companies with FDI have a significantly higher market valuation, as measured by enterprise value, compared to companies without FDI.

Here are some limitations of the study

- Data or timeframe is the limitation of this study the study reliance on data collector over a short period of time which does not capture the full effect and the fluctuation in the market evaluation of the companies which receives FDI. This factor could influence the results of the study and limiting the generalisability of the findings.
- Market valuation are often considered by investors, sentiment and external market factors like economies and geopolitics. This can cause volatility in the stock price leading to a temporary distortion in the market evaluation which does not fully and accurately represent the impact of FDI.
- The firm specific factor is the next limitation. This analysis does not occur for the variation in the firm specific factors such as corporate governance, leadership decisions

and the organisation culture within the entity. These factors can indirectly influence market valuation and financial performance of the firm.

- Inconsistent in reporting standards, different firms might follow different accounting standards or financial reporting practices. The discrepancies in the financial can lead to a challenge in calculating profitability, liquidity and efficiency between the companies with and without FDI.

The *Research methodology* of the study is a quantitative research approach based on secondary data sourced from reliable institutions like national stock exchange NSE, Bombay stock exchange BSE and corporate financial reports the data was collected for a period of seven years from 2017-2023. A comparative analysis is conducted on 40 publicly listed Indian companies which are evenly split with companies which receive FDI and companies which does not receive FDI. The companies are collected to assist the influence of foreign direct investment on the enterprise value and keep financial ratios. The analysis is performed using R programming the steps which are followed are data cleaning, exploratory data analysis EDA and multiple regression models. To ensure statistical accuracy the study includes diagnostics like multicollinearity, outlier and hetero capacity. It also applies robust standard error when necessary. This methodological framework provides a comprehensive basis for evaluating the relationship between foreign direct investment and market value of a company.

To establish a robust theoretical foundation and extensive literature review was conducted using peer reviewed article primarily source to firm SCOPUS online scientific database. All the relevant articles were selected based on the relevance to foreign direct investment, market evaluation, financial performance in emerging economies and articles relating to the theoretical framework which is used in the study. Bibliometric tools such as VOS viewer was also used to analyze the keywords trends and thematic clusters within the literature. Additionally, Mendeley reference manager was also used to organize and site sources systematically ensuring consistent and academic integrity throughout the study

1. Theoretical framework of the research

1.1 Modigliani and Miller's theory

As per Modigliani and Miller's propositions theory known from 1958, 1961 and 1963 has three important propositions, which is considered as the base of the theory Breuer and Gürtler (2008), it can be stated as:

1. Proposition I – A firm's total market value is independent of its capital structure.
2. Proposition II – The cost of equity increases with its debt-equity ratio.
3. Proposition III – A firm's total market value is independent of its dividend policy.

First Proposition– Irrelevance of the Capital Structure

In this proposition, the capital structure of the firm does not affect its market value, the M&M proposition I consist of assumptions that are under certain conditions that the firm's debt equity ratio has no effect on the firm's market value. As stated in the theory, their approaches are based on the assumption stated below

The capital market is perfect

The capital markets where trading of security takes place are considered perfect, furthermore investors can really buy and sell securities at any time they want without facing any restrictions or obstacles. Also, there are no discriminations and all participants have equal rights or access to the market. Investors have immediate and full access to the relevant data, financial reports and economic conditions of the market, and there is no asymmetry of information which ensures that no investor has an unfair advantage over others. As well as buying and selling securities does not incur cost like brokerage fees, transaction fees or administrative cost so this allows for seeing less and efficient trading that ensures the securities are priced purely based on the natural value (Miller, 1989). In a perfect capital market, the prices of securities reflect the accurate fundamental value due to the absence of inefficiency. This concept is considered as the most important in financial theories.

The First Proposition without the Effect of Taxes

This is a theory developed based on the assumption "capital market is perfect" which states that a perfect capital market that is without taxes, transaction cost or cost occurred by bankruptcy in such condition, the Structure of the firm does not affect its market value (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 1998). To illustrate this theory, they compared two firms one of it was levered,

which a company that includes debt as a part of its capital structure and another one is unlevered in that a company financed entirely by equity, which means it does not use any debt. So despite of their different financial methods, both firms generate the same level of total cash flow so Modigliani and Miller came to the conclusion that the firm's market value is purely determined based on its operational income and business risk.

The First Proposition with the Effect of Taxes

In 1963, Modigliani and Miller altered their first proposition by adding up the impact of corporate taxes which allows that real world taxation influences the financial decision. The concept is that tax shield effect in which firms with higher debt level pay less corporate taxes than those who are entirely on equity financed which makes debt financed from more valuable. The tax shield arises from the interest, detection, increased cash flow and market value (Alifani & Nugroho, 2013). The FDI contracts with this principle by serving asset, alternate to debt financing which allows firm to reduce dependency while benefiting for external capital. Similarly, FDI brings manager expertise and operational improvement, which finances cash flow and boost market value. The below figure Cost of Capital and Value of the Firm According to M&M Theorem (without taxes)

Figure 1.1 Cost of Capital and Value of the Firm Adika and Nugroho (2013)

The Second proposition – Rate of Return on Equity

The second proposition verifies the relationship between capital structure and cost of equity which states that as a firm increases its debt equity ratio the cost equity ratio also rises, creating a linear relationship between leverage and return on equity the key concept is the higher financial risk leads to higher cost of equity and increased debt rises the financial risk due to

fixed obligations which prompt equity investors to demand higher returns. FDI influences this dynamics by providing external equity financing which reduces the dependency on debt, also lower debt obligation and maintaining finance stability while balancing the capital structure.

The Second proposition without the effect of taxes

In the second proposition without taxes, the cost of equity increases similarly with the debt equity ratio due to the higher financial risk. However, the weighted average cost of the capital remains unchanged because the lower cost of debt balance rises the cost of equity. The investors understand that the higher depth increases the financial risk which leads equity investors to demand high returns (Giglio, 2022). Debt is considerably cheaper than the equity due to the contractual interest payments and lower risk. FDI brings capital, financial strategies and risk management which improve soft operational efficiency. This reduces the dependency on excessive leverage which keeps the cost of equity under control while ensuring long-term sustainability.

The Second Proposition with the Effect of Taxes

In 1963 Modigliani and Miller altered their original capital structure theory by adding corporate taxes into their theory. The authors asserted that paying interest on the debt is tax deductible which leads to a tax shield reduces a firm's taxable income and as a result, reduced its overall burden. The key concept of this proposition is the impact of taxes on capital structure. In this, unlike the original proposition of 1958, which is considered as perfect market with no taxes so the altered model states that corporate taxes exist and debt financing give tax benefits. The tax shield comes to existence because the interest paid on debt is deductible from taxable income while reducing the firm's total tax liability. As a result, the firm's weighted average cost of capital is lowered due to higher proportion of debt in the capital structure (Spahr et al., 2012)

When tax is included in capital structure analysis firms benefit by increasing the debt which leverages the tax shield effect to reduce the taxable income and lower total tax liability (Faulkender & Smith, 2013). This makes the financing more cost effective than equity as the firm increases debt and the weighted average cost of capital decreases due to the tax deductible interest payments. The second proposition with tax highlights the importance of tax shield in financial decisions. FDI alliance with the theory by reducing the debt dependency and optimizing tax advantages by announcing firm value without excessive financial risk. Foreign investment access is a strategic tool, which offers benefits, similar to debt, but with lower risk.

Figure 1.2 The Cost of Capital and Value of the Firm According to M&M (2025)

The Third propositions - Irrelevance of the Dividend policy

The third proposition states that a firm's weighted average cost of capital remains unchanged, regardless of the capital structure, which means financing with equity or debt does not affect the overall cost (Knoll, 2017). This supports the irrelevance of financial decision in determining the firm's value which depends on the operational income and investment. FDI with this theory which states as equity investment from multinational corporations, enables firms to expand, boost, productivity, and access global market without any heavy debt. FDI influences dividend policies, when foreign investors often profit investment over high payouts by reinforcing the idea that financial choices does not make any change in the firm's value with the growth prospects are strong.

1.2 The Financial Liberalization Hypothesis and its Role in Enhancing FDI Efficiency

The financial liberalization hypothesis states that the liberalization of the financial market increases the effectiveness of direct investment so that it promotes economic growth. This relationship is well supported in data driven research which emphasizes the critical role of the financial system which shapes the impact of FDI economic performance. Liberalized financial market creates efficient capital allotment, improves risk management and increases the capability in taking capacity of FDI which ultimately leads to more huge economic growth (Rasekhi & Sayedi, 2010).

Financial Liberalization and FDI Efficiency

Financial liberalization plays a pivotal role in maximizing the benefits received from FDI. In economies with underdeveloped or non-liberalized financial sectors the foreign direct investors may be having limited or even negative effects on GDP growth per capital. Initially this is due to inefficiency in financial intermediation, hindrance on Mobility and inadequate financial infrastructure. Vice versa in economies with well developed financial sectors the FDI generates positive growth effects because the capital can be more effectively allocated and investment risks are managed better (Ayouni et al., 2014).

The degree of financial system liberalization appears to be a key aspect of FDI efficiency, countries with liberalized financial markets are considered to be attracting high-quality FDI and experience great economic benefits because of such investments. Financial legalization encourages an environment to be good for foreign investment by reducing transaction cost, enhancing investor confidence and in increasing access to credit and financial services (Ayouni et al., 2014). So these factors altogether contribute to the efficiency and productivity of FDI.

The Impact of Financial Liberalization

The impact of financial liberation on foreign direct investment is varied particularly in emerging markets. Financial liberalization creates increased mobility, attracting foreign investors and boosting economic growth; however, it also consists of risk, especially in countries with underdeveloped financial systems. Financial liberalization has significantly boosted FDI in countries like India where rules and norms have strengthened the connection between GDP growth and FDI attraction (Divakar, 2024). By easing restrictions on Flow, reducing regulatory barriers, and improving the overall investing environment, financial liberation has made India a more attractive destination for foreign investors. Moreover, financial liberalization has facilitated technology transfer and manager expertise which enables local firms to increase their productivity and competitiveness (Wang & Luo, 2023)

. Foreign investors bring advanced technology and best practices for effective business that helps to modernize domestic industry. This integration of foreign expertise with localities has improved innovation, efficiency, and global competitiveness in various sectors in the market (Kadli, 2023).

Figure 1.3 Financial liberalisation theory Kadli (2023)

1.3 Ohlson Valuation Model

The Ohlson valuation model (OVM) is widely used in a financial valuation framework which integrates with book value, earnings, and residual income to assess the full value of the firm. Traditionally this model is applied to stock evaluation also the OBM model can be adapted to evaluate foreign direct investment opportunities by adding a financial matrix along with broader economic and qualitative factors so by refining the model to take part in the complexities of the cross border investment in which investors can gain a more comprehensive understanding on FDI attractiveness. The below shown visual diagram on the application of Ohlson model account for non accounting information to influence a company stock value.

Figure 1.4 Application of Ohlson model Schaefer (2018)

Financial metrics in OVM

The Ohlson valuation model (OVM) gives a structured approach to financial valuation by understanding the key metrics such as book value, earnings, and residual income so when these metrics are adapted for foreign direct investment analysis, these financial indicators offer us valuable insight into the financial health and long-term profitability of the investment targets

Book value and earnings

The book value of the company refers its net value, which is calculated as total asset minus liability in the context of FDI analysis book value is essential measure of financial stability which helps investor to assess the underlying strength of a firm's balance sheet so a higher book value generally shows how strong a companies asset base is and it makes the company more attractive as an investment target. earnings on other hand, represents a company's profitability over a given period of time. In the OMV the earnings is considered as a key determinant of stock price and overall valuation which provides insights into a firm's operational efficiency for an FDI decision-making the consistent and growing earnings suggest a financially sound company with sustainable revenue streams, which reduces investment risks so investor analyzing FDI opportunities prioritize firms with stock earning potential (Ayadi & Ojo, 2015). So the businesses are more likely to generate long-term returns and contribute positively to GDP growth in the domestic country.

Residual income approach

Residual income is a clarified profitability measure that accounts for a company's ability to generate returns beyond its cost of equity considering the traditional earnings based models, which only consider net income but the residual income approach evaluates whether a firm is creating economic value for the shareholder after covering the expected return on capital. In FDI assessment, incorporating residual value into the OVM allows the investor to differentiate between high performing firms and companies that may appear profitable, but also failed to generate excess return, so a positive residual income indicates that a company is creating value higher than its capital cost, which makes it an attractive investment target. Vice versa negative residual income suggests inefficiency or inability to generate sufficient return on capital which signals potential risk for foreign investors (Song & Lee, 2023). By combining residual income into FDI evaluation, the investors can gain a more clear understanding of a company's financial health beyond its basic earning reports so this approach helps the investors identify business with strong value creation potential so it ensures that FDI contributes to economic growth while maximizing investor return.

1.4 Regulatory Framework and Factors Influencing FDI Inflows in Indian States

Foreign direct investment FDI in India is regulated using a structured framework which consists of multiple acts, policies and guidelines which has made a significant change in the economy since the economic reforms of the 1990s. This reform has made a major shift from a reserve economy to a more liberalized and globally integrated one. The Indian government has constantly worked towards creating a more investor friendly environment while ensuring that national interests are protected.

Foreign trade (development and regulation) act, 1992

The foreign trade (development and regulation) act, 1992 gives the central government the power to develop and implement foreign trade policy and those policies place a vital role in regulating India's international trade and creating a positive environment for foreign direct investment by introducing flexible policy adaptation in which the act allows the government to respond quickly to global economic trends, which ensures India's trade policies alliance with growing market conditions. Additionally it makes import export regulation, licensing procedure, and trade promotion initiatives, which collectively contributes in increasing India's attractiveness as an investment destination (Pal & Kaushik, 2024).

New industry policy, 1991

The new industry policy has shown a significant transformation in India's economic landscape by accompanying an era of liberalization, privatization and globalization. This policy played as an instrument in reducing administrative burdens that previously was an obstacle in business operation and investment inflow. By disowning the strict licensing regimen, loosening restrictions on foreign capital and opening multiple sectors to private, and for investment for this policy, significantly contributed to India's economic expansion, which paved the way for FDI liberalization, technological advancement, and increased market competition, which ultimately announced the dynamics and market driven economy (Shekhawat, 2017).

Foreign Exchange Management Act (FEMA), 1999

The foreign exchange management act (FEMA) of 1999 was established to replace the more restrictive foreign exchange regulation act (FERA), which made a significant shift in India's approach to foreign exchange regulation. The FEMA focuses on liberalizing and simplifying the regulatory framework which governs for an exchange transaction for making it more investor friendly. By removing the strict ownership regulation that previously limited foreign investment, the FEMA facilitated the smooth entry and operation of foreign firms in India. The act reduced bureaucratic hindrance, streamlining, approval processes, and ensuring greater flexibility in capital flow, which in turn enhanced investors confidences. In that way, these reforms played a vital role in boosting foreign direct investment which attracted multinational corporations so that integrated India more deeply into the global economy (Majumdar, 2007).

The Companies Act, 2013

The company act of 2013 is considered as a foundation of corporate governance in India, which is embedded with the key principle that indirectly supports foreign direct investment by strengthening the investor protection and making a transparent business environment. This act establishes a robust regulator framework by outlining the shareholder rights which answers that investors from both domestic and foreign have clear, legal protections and mechanisms for problem redressal. Moreover, this act defines the duties and responsibilities of directors, mandating, accountability, and ethical business practices to safeguard the stakeholders interests. These measures altogether enhanced investors confidence which made India, a more attractive and reliable destination for foreign investment because businesses operating under this framework are considered to be more transparent and well regulated, and aligned with international's best practices (Shikha, 2017).

Factors Influencing FDI Inflows in Indian States

Foreign direct investment in flow can vary across different states due to multiple reasons like economy, infrastructural and policy related factors. Some states are attracts higher FDI due to their business friendly environment, development of the infrastructure and skill to workforce while some receive less. Analysing and understanding these factors can help to explain the regional disparity behind FDI and flows and the impact on economic growth.

Table 1.1

FDI inflow distribution amongst Indian states RBI(2025)

Rank	State	2022-23 (USD Million)	2023-24 (USD Million)	2024-25 (April- Dec) (USD Million)	Cumulative Equity Inflow (USD Million)	% of Total FDI Equity Inflow
1	Maharashtra	14,806	15,116	16,651	85,737	31%
2	Karnataka	10,429	6,571	4,496	55,528	20%
3	Gujarat	4,714	7,300	5,566	44,767	16%
4	Delhi	7,534	6,523	4,453	36,169	13%
5	Tamil Nadu	2,169	2,436	2,903	13,841	5%
6	Haryana	2,600	1,908	2,843	12,572	5%
7	Telangana	1,303	3,029	2,071	9,845	4%
8	Rajasthan	910	265	284	2,628	1%
9	Uttar Pradesh	420	334	307	1,942	1%
10	Jharkhand	6	11	0	2,667	1%

Economic and industrial strength

This criteria signifies Greater influence on the amount of flow of foreign direct investment. States like Maharashtra, Karnataka and Gujarat among the leading in FDI due to its well established finance, IT and manufacturing sector. Mumbai the financial capital of India causes the headquarters of many multinational corporation and major financial institutions making this place a primary destination for foreign investment. Karnataka it's capital Bangalore is known as Silicon Valley of India which attracts a significant investment in technological sector. Gujarat with a stronger manufacturing base includes automobile, petrol chemicals and textiles which is a preferred location for global market.

Infrastructure and connectivity

A well developed infrastructure of the crucial factors for foreign direct investment as this allows a smooth operation of business in the reduced cost related to logistics and transportation. Maharashtra and Gujarat benefits from excellent Road network, International Airport and major ports like Jawaharlal Neru port and Mura port. Karna and Gaana have developed IT parks and specialised economy zone to attract foreign investment.

Skilled workforce and labour availability

The availability of the skilled workforce is a key determination of foreign direct investment states like Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Maharashtra are home too many prestigious educational Institute engineering colleges and research Centres which produces high-quality graduates. Bangalore Kama Chennai and Pune have become global hubs for IT and soft development due to depressants of will educator workforce is seen as one of the important factors for foreign direct investment. Because the availability of well skilled and knowledgeable graduate is important for the foreign companies in order them to move on without worrying on the recruitment process.

Government policies and initiatives

One of the other important factor is business friendly and environment states like Gujarat, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu have introduced business friendly policies and simplified regulation process. It also offers tax benefits to attract foreign investors. Particularly Gujarat has created a strong investment climate through initiatives like vibrant Gujarat Summit which promotes trade partnership and foreign collaborations.

Proximity to trade routes and market

Geographical location is also of the important factor which can be accessible domestically and internationally. States like Maharashtra, Gujarat and Tamil Nadu have a strategic coastal location which allows them to access global shipping route and facilitate import export activities. Major cities like Mumbai Kama Chennai, Ahmedabad and Surat have a strong linkage with International trade and it's one of the prime destination for foreign businesses.

Conclusion

The disparity in FDI flows among the Indian states can be divided into several factors like industrial development, infrastructure quality, available workforce, government policies

and trade access accessibility. Maharashtra Karna Gujarat received higher FDI due to stronger economic base and also invest our friendly policies, skilled workforce and higher quality infrastructure. While states like darkened and Rajasthan received FDI lower due to the week infrastructure lack of industrial diversification and also policy challenges. And Uttar Pradesh our states with bureaucratic hurdles and also regulatory delays this is faced – and challenge in order to streamline the businesses. And states like Rajasthan have fewer institutions that provides and produce skilled professional in the field of IT and engineering as a result these states this out attractive investments from high-tech companies.. lastly 10 Uttar Pradesh face challenges due to poor road connectivity and also limited availability of industrial parks.

1.5 Literature review

The next part of our study is to analyse various literature articles which are publicly available to get a deeper understanding on our topic foreign direct investment and its impact on the market valuation of Indian listed firms. All the article which we collected are open-source article. The article was analysed and the keywords that found out from each article. Articles with the similar key words are group together for further analysis. This process will give us a deeper understanding into the literature landscape of foreign direct investment. The below table contains the list of authors and the keyword grouped among 10 different categories. These categories were carefully selected and a group in order to understand the dynamics of foreign direct investment. The above table has helped us to compare different papers amongst each other to get a deeper understanding on our topic. The foreign direct investment has played a vital role in shaping economic landscapes across different nations, particularly in emerging economies author highlights that the interplay between FDI and the balance of payment and capital and flow emphasises its influence on the trade dynamics. Hasan et al. (2024) extended his study by focusing on institutional quality and stock market development tenant around the activity and attractiveness of FDI in emerging countries. In this paper provided a detailed analysis of FDI trends and determinants In the emerging economics. In a study he identified main factors such as market size, infrastructure and political stability some of the key driver so foreign direct investment. For detailed literature review please look into the below table 1.2

Table 1.2

Analysis of literature review (created by author using SCOPUS)

Group	Authors	Keywords
FDI Determinants and Economic Growth	Jacob and Jiji (2021)	FDI, Balance of Payments, Capital Inflows, Trade Dynamics, Institutional Quality, Emerging Economies, Economic Growth, Capital Accumulation, Technology Transfer
	Hasan, M. A., et al. (2024)	
	Sharma, S., et al. (2023)	
	Jayadi and Prasetyo (2022)	
	Fernandes, A. (2024)	
FDI in Emerging Markets	Purkayastha and Filatotchev (2023)	FDI, Emerging Economies, Foreign Equity Valuations, Productivity Ratios, Determinants, Broader Economic Impacts
	Su, Z., et al. (2023)	
Innovation and Spillover Effects	Vujanović, N., et al. (2022)	FDI, Spillover Effects, Innovation, Knowledge Firms, Technological Spillover, Innovation, Employment Growth
	Nosova (2022)	
Sustainability and Environmental Impact	Da Mota and Da Silva Ferreira Neto Rodrigues (2023)	FDI, Sustainability, Social and Environmental Welfare, Trade, Carbon Emissions, Renewable Energy, GDP, Emissions
	Güvercin, D. (2019)	
	Amidi and Hishan (2022)	
High-Tech and Sector-Specific FDI	Dong, M. (2024)	Inward FDI, Political Connections, High-Tech Sector, Employment Growth, Retailing, Job Creation, Unemployment
	Nosova (2022)	
	Kannaiah and Selvam (2014)	
Market Valuation and Capital Flows	Le and Park (2019)	FDI, Capital Inflows, Market Valuation, Technology Transfer, Debt Financing, Financial Crises
	Luk and Zheng (2019)	
Regional and Strategic Development	Osinubi and Ajide (2022)	FDI, Economic Complexity, Regional Priorities, Financial Stability, Capital Account Policies
	Yakubovskiy, S., et al. (2019)	
	Dua and Verma (2023)	
Finance and Globalization Trends	P. Tiwari (2016)	FDI, Globalization, Industrial Growth, Portfolio Composition, Asset Valuation, Finance Research
	Goyal and Sharma (2018)	
	Arnold et al. (2001)	
Bibliometric and Analytical Studies	Nazzal, A., et al. (2023)	FDI, Bibliometric Analysis, MNC Performance, Internationalization
Comprehensive Review of FDI Impacts	Amidi and Hishan (2022)	FDI, Economy, Environment, Technology, Productivity, Energy

Similarly, Jayadi and Prasetyo (2022), as discussed, the positive correlation between foreign direct investment and economic growth in the emerging countries. Fernandes (2024) in this paper the author examines FDI in Brazilian economy and its contribution to the economic growth through capital accumulation and technological transfer this study also alliance with. Study on empirical analysis which explores the FDI growth in China and India are the two major FDI in flow countries showcase saying how FDI finances the productivity and the industrial competitiveness within the countries market

Purkayastha and Filatotchev (2023), in the paper the authors have explored the foreign equity evaluations are influenced by institutional decision. This study is complimented by Su et al., (2023) where the authors delve deeper into the role of inflow of FDI in the entrepreneurial productivity and focusing on the opportunity to increase the measure of economic impact. The FDI contribution to innovation and knowledge is a recurring theme in many literatures for example. Vujanović et al. (2022) in a study as found out the dual role of FDI access below over effect and supporting knowledge creation in the firms this study also suggested that the presence of FDI might and innovation capacity of the local firms by enabling the access to advanced technology. This paper goes on to argue that high-tech FDI is an instrument in modernising the economy and enhancing the global competitiveness of the company.

Foreign direct investment and its relationship between the sustainability has been gaining attention Da Mota & Da Silva Ferreira Neto Rodrigues (2023), investigated the social and the environmental implication of foreign direct investment India study they found out that many companies advocate their policy in order to allow with sustainable development goals. Even though the FDI can drive the economy, the companies are more concentrator to promote social welfare and environmental sustainability. Güvercin (2019) in a study Iela is the impact of foreign direct investment trade on carbon emission and renewable energy adoption. This study highlights a significant potential of foreign direct investment in support of transition towards greener economies.

Kannaiah and Selvam (2014) in the study, they analysed how FDI generates employment opportunities and improve job qualities in India. Their findings illustrate the potential of sector specific FDI to address the social economic challenges such as unemployment and income inequality. To align with your study Nosova (2022) in the article as pointed out that FDI acts as an important factor in driving innovation and also helps the employment growth in high tech sector.

Le & Park (2019) and Luk & Zheng (2019) both author investigator relationship between FDI and the capital inflow which leads to the increase of market valuation of the

company. Le & Park (2019) found out that the role of FDI increases the investors, confidence which interns boost the market evaluation of the company while Luk & Zheng (2019) while the author analysed how FDI influences the debt financing and the financial stability and how these contribute to the companies market evaluation in both of the study the author has found out that the FDI has a significant impact on the market valuation of the company

Moreover, Osinubi & Ajide (2022) the authors examine the role of FDI in driving the economic complexity and also helping in the regional development. The author also found out that the market cluster such as MINT and BRICS some of the markets which are crucial for foreign direct investment as they attract more foreign companies towards the domestic market. Nazzal et al., (2023) in their paper adopted a bibliometric approach to analyse the impact of foreign direct investment on the multinational corporation performance. Just found out the company used internalization strategies to incorporate foreign direct investment. Their study categorised foreign direct investment and their impacts based on the entry modes and performance matrix which offer the detailed overview over the trends and patterns of FDI research.

Market Reaction to FDI Announcements: Evidence from Emerging Markets

Market reaction to the foreign direct investment announcement in the emerging markets and particularly when it comes to India, it has a distinct pattern which are influenced by various other variables. In the study found that Indian corporate announcement of foreign direct investment through mergers and acquisition often collect favourable market reaction which is contrasting to the mature markets which indicates a very distinct to behaviour difference in the market response between the emerging and the developed country (Duppati & Locke, 2012). From the above literature article we can understand that the author is arguing that the company announcement of foreign direct investment through merger accusation generally have a positive impact on the market evaluation which might be due to the factors of possible growth, efficiency or profitability improvements. However, the author also found that the reaction was different between mature markets and emerging markets. Similarly in the article Barbopoulos et al., (2014) the author has indicated that when United Kingdom companies invest in Indian companies through FDI the announcement is seen as a positive market reaction even though the emerging markets include political risk and corruption. Results from an empirical study which was carried out by (Ding & Sun, 1997) identified that on average the stock market reacts positively and significantly to the FDI announcement with the additional returns of 0.49 percentage on day 0 and accumulate to abnormal return of 0.96% over two days 0 and 1. The

author carried on the research and found out that not only companies from the same industry reacts but companies from different industries also react same to FDI even if the FDI is an independent investment or a joint venture. For the study also identified that the host country or the country from which the FDI in flow is made does not have a significant effect on the market only the announcement of FDI has a greater effect. The author controlled the study by saying that investors see this as a profit opportunity and to earn abnormal returns by buying the stock before the announcement and also selling it after five days in order to make maximum returns from the FDI announcement.

In the study Singh & Singh(2017), the author examines how the Indian stock market reacts to the announcement of FDI in the form of merger and acquisition. The author uses effective market hypothesis and with his findings. The author suggest that the Indian market is a semi strong market where the stock price often instantly and fully reflect on the all publicly available information this factor make it an an event not to earn abnormal returns. This study identifies that the Indian stock market not a semi strong effective market during the announcement. This means that the stock prices do not change immediately. Based on the results from the author Indian market might show slow or delayed reaction to the FDI announcement. To contradict Singh & Singh (2017) and Bhattacharjee and De (2022) in this research article the author suggest that Indian market do incorporate corporate news very quickly to employ a certain level of market efficiency your author has used even study methodology to analyse both stock pricing and trading volume changes in response to the corporate announcement. The Indian market responding efficiently to the firm specific news might also react promptly to the FDI announcement.

FDI's Role in Enhancing Firm Competitiveness and Market Value

Foreign direct investment place is a vital role in strengthening a firm's competitiveness and it also help the boost the market value of the company particularly the emerging economy. FDI helps to bring capital, advanced technology and also manager expertise which improve the firm's operational efficiency innovation and global market access. In a study carried by Sekuloska (2015) the author highlights the importance of high-quality FDI which drastically improves the innovation, firms' competitiveness and also the market value. It also signifies that FDI brings technological transfer is one of the greatest benefits which can flow through the foreign firms. This study mainly focuses on the FDI relationship on the firms competitiveness. Highlights that FDI place a crucial role and the study also is the technological growth innovation improvement in the company.

In a similar study carried out by Alvarez and Marin (2013) the author examines how multinational enterprise contributes to the competitiveness of the firms in the developing countries through the process of technology absorption and creation. This study goes on highlighting the importance of both internal capabilities and also external factors are important to the companies announcement. The paper goes on explaining that a firms ability to integrate high-tech market coupled with their ability to adopt a greater technology place a wide role in achieving their competitiveness on the global stage. From this paper it is understood that FDI can drive technological advancement and innovation in the host country thereby also improving the firms competitiveness and also improve the market evaluation of the company.

Similarly, another literature article Pant (2014) the author stated that developing countries are now increasingly open to the foreign direct investment. The main aim of this company is to enhance the competitive nest in the domestic market by using the technology and organisational skill which are achieved through FDI. The study also states that companies cannot achieve the same effect by just buying the foreign technology but they can achieve this through integration of foreign firms in the form of FDI. FDI has also increased the competitiveness between the firms and it also have a strong effect on the market valuation of the companies. Next another article Dimelis (2005) investigate this spillover effects of foreign direct investment on the growth of domestic firms in a developing country specifically Greece during the late 90s. With the help of advantages gained during FDI the companies are improving the production based on new technologies and now they are financial structure and the market structure has also improved due to the synergies which are attained during foreign direct investment. The study also empirically analysed the Greeks manufacturing sector and found out that there was 7% increase over five years after FDI which highlights the positive relationship between FDI and the company growth. The firms competitiveness relies on one of the main feature that is the absorption capacity of the company in leveraging the impacts which are gained during FDI on the firms growth.

A similar paper explores how spillover effect the foreign direct investment in Polish corporate sector. The study distinguished between horizontal spillover which is from domestic firms within the same industry and verticals spillover which is from foreign firms to the domestic industry. The study found out that domestic firms benefit from the presence of foreign firms. FDI often brings R&D investment it increases the cooperative pressure and announce the backwards spillover and also improve the market power by fostering the words spillover. These papers suggest that spillover effect achieved with FDI can improve the competitiveness and the productivity of the domestic firms which also ultimately improves the market value of the

domestic firm. This paper also emphasises more on absorption capability and the sector specific factors which influence this spillover effect Marcin, K. (2007).

Analysis of Most Cited Articles on the Impact of FDI and Market Valuation

In the section of the research, the author will discuss the highly cited papers from the collection of all literature articles which the author has collected for the study. This will help to understand the relationship between foreign direct investment and market evaluation. Can discuss why this articles have gained significant attention in this field. The below figure consist the top 10 literatures which were cited by other authors.

Figure 1.5 Most cited article (created by author)

The articles from the collection in the above figure has a significant higher count of citations. This articles provide us with the valuable insight into the factors influencing foreign direct investment and its impact on various aspects of economic development, corporate behaviour and market performance making them a highly relevant topic in order to assist the influence of foreign direct investment on the market evaluation of publicly listed companies. For instance Tamazian and Rao (2009) work on the relationship between economics, financial and institutional development along with environmental degradation of a different perspective on how the economy borders in conclusion with the developing countries which also includes India. A similar paper Baltagi et al., (2008) the author has investigated the role of financial development and also the openness of the companies which is one of the crucial factors to study on FDI and what influence that's it I have on the market evaluation of the firms.

Paul and Benito (2017) as reviewed the outward FDI from the emerging markets which includes China, it provides us a comprehensive view of the trends and also the factors which drive the FDI in flow and how the FDI can impact the market evaluation of a company. Additionally, to this the articles like Asongu et al., (2018) dive deep into the topic and the important of country specific factors which includes governance and infrastructure which can also have a relationship between FDI and market evaluation especially in the fast growing countries like India (Sasidharan & Kathuria, 2011).

Study on the interaction between foreign directive investment and R&D in the India's manufacturing sector and understanding how the foreign direct investment can lead to value creation within the firms.

Both papers Goergen et al., (2003) and Phong and Hoang, (2019) has analysed close related topics by exploring corporate edition making, dividends and broader economic effect of the globalisation. These factors are the integral parts for understanding the foreign direct investments effects. Lastly Buckley et al., (2015) has analysed the cross, broader accusation and outward FDI in the emerging markets, especially in the BRICS countries which can have a direct effect on the market evaluation of the company. These authors also found out that FDI influence the investors, confidence and corporate data G which intern increases the market evaluation of the company. All these articles have been frequently cited because of their importance in the empirical work and their ability to share the light on different aspects of foreign direct investment on the economic outcomes and the corporate outcomes. This analysis help us to understand how FDI can affect the market evaluation of a publicly listed company.

The below figure 1.6 is VOSviewer network visualisation which shows the co-occurrences of the keywords. From the image you can see different concentration of the nodes. The central nodes are foreign direct investment and FDI which depicts the main topic of our study. These are highly interconnected indicating the core importance surrounding this. The other keywords are related at concepts like economical growth, financial development, globalisation, and trade openness. These key words suggest the importance of the influence which has on FDI, the prominence of India has the largest node suggesting that is the main focus of the study along with emerging economies and countries like Brazil, South Africa Africa, and organisational countries like BRICS.

Figure 1.6 Keywords visual network (created by author using Vos viewer)

The figure and the keywords are divided into several colour clusters. The first cluster is green cluster which is economic impact with the keywords like economic growth, globalisation, trade openness, human capital and institutional quality. This cluster suggest us that FDI is not only about the financial flow in the company, but it is also intertwined with the broader economic factors. For instance, a stronger economic growth might positively affect the FDI on the companies value. The second cluster is red cluster which is centred over the topic India with the keywords like emerging economies, China, Brazil, South Africa and BRICS. The connection of this cluster to the topic is context of the emerging market and FDI comparing the India's experience with other countries experience to get detailed insight and the regulatory environment of specific industry and across different countries. The blue cluster explains as the market dynamics and other financial with the keywords like market evaluation, capital structure, financial markets, financial development and the stock market development. This research is the most relevant cluster to the authors topic emphasises the link between foreign direct investment and financial performance of the company and what influence does the FDI have then the company have access to the foreign capital. Up Next, the author will analyse the density visualisation from the VOSviewer software in the below figure

Figure 1.7 Density map of Keywords (created by author using Vos viewer)

The Above figure contains density visualisation which itself says to identify the core theme of the research topic. It also helps us to visually identify the strong concentration of literature and research activity around the specific keyword for example from the above figure it's clearly evident that the keywords like foreign direct investment and India are bright yellow areas which indicates highly dense and the centre topic of our study along with other keywords like economic growth and FDI also follows a similar pattern. This suggest us that the main body of the research is to the relationship between FDI and economic development in the case of a company or the entire country. The spread of the density, two words keywords like globalisation, financial development and market evaluation indicates as there are will explode the topics in relation to FDI. This helps to support the relevance to the author study by influencing FDI on the market valuation of publicly listed companies in India. The density map helped to effectively visualise the trends and the connection across the research area. The below figure is a visualisation of a evolving landscape of the research topic

Figure 1.9 Country visualisation of the literature (created by author using Vos viewer)

The visualisation depicts the biographic coupling of the country name. Highlights the interconnectedness of the research on FTA and the market evaluation across different countries. The prominent India indicates the study focus on India frequently share a common source with the researchers on the other countries. The Indian node have a stronger connections with the countries like United Kingdom, United States and Australia suggesting that the call investigating FDI in this region and often realise on the same foundational literature. This may also be due to the reason of shared the theoretical framework and mythological approaches or even data source. Next the cluster of European nation and emerging economic suggest as the degree of the regional focus in the research the overall utilisation emphasise the global nature of foreign direct research and importance of considering a international perspective. We can also see some of the countries which are FDI hotspots for the host nation so the researchers are likely to study these countries and how FDI impact a specific company and its market valuation.

2 Methodology of the research

This study adopts a quantitative research approach to analyse the impact of foreign direct investment on the market valuation of the Indian listed companies. This research is mainly based on secondary data which are collected from verified online sources such as national stock exchange (NSE), Bombay stock exchange (BSE), companies, financial statements and other reliable financial database. This study employees a comparative analysis to examine the difference between the companies which receives FDI and which do not receive FDI focusing mainly on the enterprise value as the primary market evaluation matrix for the companies.

The data will be extracted from the online sources and cross verified with the companies financial statements. The selected companies will be categorised into two main groups like firms with FDI and firms without FDI allowing us to assist the influence of FDI in financial performance and valuation of the company.

By leveraging the data which are collected from the sources. The study will issue high reliability and also accuracy. The financial analysis the study metrology follows compared to approach which is distinguish between the companies which receive FDI and which does not receive FDI to evaluate the extent and impact of foreign investment on their market evaluation. Keeping the primary focus on enterprise value to capture both companies equity and debt components which provides a hostile view of the firms worth. The data set will cover multiple financial indicators relevant to the corporate evaluation and investment attractiveness enabling to understand a deepen into the relationship between FDI and the firms performance. The data has been collected. It will be systematically cross verified using the company balance sheet and other financial filings to maintain the consistency.

The classification of the companies which receives every year in which do not receive FDI will help to structure the examination and the differences between them the evaluation of two groups and helps to assess whether FDI has an impact. The key objective of the research to determine whether the companies which receive FDI exhibits higher market evaluation compared to the companies which doesn't to address this the study will analyse various financial indicators such as profitability, liquidity, leverage without specific focusing on financial ratios of an individual section. These indicators are expected to provide a deep insight into the companies financial health and the market perception once the companies receive FDI.

The research will be structured around the following hypothesis that as companies with FDI have significantly higher valuations then companies without FDI. The expected outcomes

is the firms receiving FDI demonstrate superior. Several statistical analysis will be done on the data said to conclude the hypothesis. If the statistical analysis confirms a strong and positive relationship between FDI and the enterprise value, it will support our hypothesis and the argument around it it leads to FDI improve the market evaluation by increasing the firm stability but if there is a show insignificant or impact it would indicate that FDI alone does not necessarily drive. The company is enterprise value. There are also other additional factors which may contribute to the company's performance

Selection and Formulation of Financial Ratios for Market Valuation Analysis

In the context of assisting the influence of foreign direct investment on the market valuation of public listed companies the financial ratio serves as one of the crucial tools for evaluating the company performance. This ratios offered a standardised method for comparing companies irrespective of their size and industry. The race shows provide available insight into the profitability, liquidity, efficiency and the market perception of the company. The purpose of taking and analysing the financial ratios is to understand how the different aspects of a company financial performance can relate to the overall market evaluation.

In this research the author focuses on key financial ratios which are commonly used in assessing a company operational effectiveness, market performance and stability. By examining the following ratios the study games to provide a clear understanding on the potential on how foreign direct investment in flow affects the market evaluation. The following figure contains the financial ratios which will be used in the analysis and following the formulas and the rational behind the use of the ratio and inclusion in the model will be explained.

The below figure contains all the eight chosen ratios which will be used to for performing statistical analysis for this research. Now the author will be explaining how these ratios are calculated and what are the significance of these ratios below

Figure 2.1 Key financial ratios used for analysis (created by author)

Return on equity

Return equity is a profitability ratios which helps to measure the companies ability to generate profits based from its shareholder equity. It shows how well the company uses the invested capital to generate the earnings. Usually a higher return on equity indicates that the company is effectively utilising its capital to generate the revenue. The below formula of ROE is calculated (Ichsani & Suhardi, 2015)

$$\text{Return on Equity (ROE)} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Shareholder's Equity}} \quad (2.1)$$

When a company receives FDI, it receives additional capital which helps to expand its operation, increase its efficiency or also for manufacturing companies it can result in launching of new products. This can potentially increase the company earnings and when it's divided by equity, it can result in higher return on equity. The investors might interpret the return on equity as an indicator on how profitable is the company and how it's used realising it's capital which can lead to higher market valuation.

Return on asset

Return on asset can you help to measure how the company use its asset to generate profit, It is calculated by dividing the company net income by its total asset generally higher return on asset indicates the company is utilising its assets efficiently and converting the to generate more profits. The formula for ROA is calculated by (Jewell & Mankin, 2011)

$$\text{Return on Assests (ROA)} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total Assets}} \quad (2.2)$$

FDI can often lead to infusion of capital which improves the companies asset base such as acquiring new missionaries and expanding its infrastructure. Assets in the sense not only the tangible assets but also intangible assets like intellectual property can also be attended during foreign direct investment. If the company is able to generate higher amount of revenue based on the newly infused asset, it can increase their return on asset ratio indicating the better utilisation of asset which might lead to the increase of market valuation

Current ratio

The current ratio is a liquidity ratio. It helps to measure the companies ability to cover a short-term liability with a short-term assets. Usually a higher ratio suggest that the company is in better position to cover a short term obligations. The below formula for current ratio is calculated (Eljelly, 2004).

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}} \quad (2.3)$$

When a company receives FDI receives a increase in cash flow of cash or other assets, which can often improve the liquidity of the company. The additional capital which the company receives can help to pay off short-term liability and improve the current ratio. Increase in the current ratio after FDI suggest that the company is now managing it short term liabilities better and investors can see the companies ability to handle financial obligations which intern leads to increase in the market value of the company.

Quick ratio

Quick ratio is also called as acid test ratio it is one of the liquidity ratios as it includes inventory from current assets. Quick ratio indicates how a company's ability to meet short-term obligations without relying on the inventory. Formula for quick ratio is given below (Sari et al., 2022)

$$\text{Quick Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets} - \text{Inventory}}{\text{Current Liabilities}} \quad (2.4)$$

FDI can strengthen the company liquidity position by providing additional capital flow which allows us to cover short-term liability with its most liquid assets without interfering with the inventory. An infusion of cash can improve the quick ratio and indicate a stronger position to meet short-term applications. Generally speaking a higher ratio is positively taken by the investor perspective which can lead to attract the market and potentially raising the value of the company.

Asset turnover ratio

Asset turnover ratio measure on how efficiently accompany use asset to generate its revenue and higher asset turnover ratio of an indicates the company is utilising its assets efficiently to generate sales (Utami, 2017)

$$\text{Asset Turnover} = \frac{\text{Revenue}}{\text{Average Total Assets}} \quad (2.5)$$

FDI can provide company with the necessary capital to invest in technology, infrastructure or any other assets which can announce the operational efficiency of the company. This can lead to more efficient utilisation of the assets which can result in the improvement of asset turnover ratio. FDI can help the company to increase their revenue in relative to their asset base which positively influenced the investor which can also lead to higher market valuation.

Price to earnings ratio

The price to earnings ratio is a market based ratio which helps to compare the company market price per share to its earning special. It helps to identify on how much the investors are willing to pay for each dollar of earnings from the company. It helps to provide a deeper insight into the market expectation of the companies future earnings. The formula for calculating P/E ratio is given below (Ohlson, 1983).

$$\frac{P}{E} = \frac{\text{Market price per share}}{\text{Book value per share}} \quad (2.6)$$

FDI can increase the market perception of the companies growth and even increased future profitability. As a foreign investor brings capital into the company it might be perceived as a better growth opportunity for the company which usually results in higher PE ratio.. hi P

ratio can signal that the company is viewed positively in the market which could increase the market value of the company

Price to book ratio

Price to book ratio helps us to compare the company market price per share to which book value per share it helps to gain an insight into the market value of the company relative to which net asset value. The formula is given below (Penman, 1996).

$$\frac{P}{B} = \frac{\text{Market price per share}}{EPS} \quad (2.7)$$

FDI might signal positive future growth prospect for the company which helps the promote the value of the company more highly than its book value. Usually for investors bring both capital and also business expertise which can help the company to improve operationally and also an increase in the market position. This can lead to the increase in the price to book ratio as investors are willing to pay more for the company stocks, then it's actual book value.

Debt to equity ratio

That equity ratio helps us to measure the company financial leverage by comparing the total debt to Tushar oldest equity. Generally a higher ratio suggest that the company is more often relies on debt to finance operation which might usually result in financial risk. The for calculation is given below (Kurniawan, 2021)

$$\frac{D}{E} = \frac{\text{Total Debt}}{\text{Total Equity}} \quad (2.8)$$

FDI can reduce the reliance on debt financing by providing additional capital. This influx of equity can lower the debt to equity ratio indicating a more balanced and less financially risk structure. This could be taken as a positive effect and the investors see the company as less leverage and more financially stable company which might positively impact its market value.

Process of data collection

In this part of the research, the process of collecting data will be thoroughly explained. In order to contact a good analysis of the impact on FDI on the market evaluation of the company listed in India the first step in the author study is to identify and select the companies with and without FDI. To ensure the accuracy and the reliability the author relayed on multiple official and credible data sources to identify the companies which received FDI which doesn't

receive FDI. Reserve bank of India maintains a detailed report on foreign investment in influence into India. The reports are classified as foreign direct investment annual reports, foreign direct investment circular and other related documents. Next the department of promotion of industry and internal trade this department comes under the ministry of commerce and industry and government of India it publishes FDI statistics sector wise in flow data and other related FDI policies. The author explored additional government sources such as SEBI and Ministry of corporate affairs for company filings on foreign investment disclosure. Next the newsletters and articles were also examined which includes new portal, financial reports and research articles published from reputed source. Lastly, the stock exchange filings that the company would have filed the detailed financial statement and disclosure which includes also foreign direct investment details. With the help of all the above websites the author was able to collect a group of companies with and without FDI for further analysis.

With the help of the above sources a list compiling of 20 companies with FDI and 20 companies without FDI were collected. The next step in the study is to gather the key financial ratios for analysis from the selected companies. These financial ratios include ROA, ROE, current ratio, quick ratio, asset turnover ratio, price to book ratio, price to earnings ratio and debt to equity ratio.

The following table comprises a list of prominent Indian companies that are most likely to have foreign direct investment. The below company is a big company and due to their size and global operation and also the market presence of this companies it attracts foreign capital in the forms of FDI. Many companies are a subsidiary companies of multinational corporations who have joint venture with the foreign firms. These things contribute to their growth and success in the Indian market. This foreign investments place a crucial role in shaping the financial performance of the market values of this company.

Table 2.1

List of companies with FDI (Sourced from 2017 to 2023 NSE and company disclosures of India)

Serial No	Company Name	Ticker Symbol
1	A B B	ABB
2	Abbott India	ABBOTINDIA
3	Astrazeneca Pharma India	ASTRAZEN
4	Bata India	BATAINDIA
5	Bosch	BOSCHLTD
6	Castrol India	CASTROLIND
7	Colgate-Palmolive India	COLPAL
8	Gillette India	GILLETTE
9	Hindustan Unilever	HINDUNILVR
10	Honeywell Automation India	HONAUT
11	Maruti Suzuki India	MARUTI
12	Nestle India	NESTLEIND
13	Oracle Financial Services Software	OFSS
14	P & G Hygiene & Health Care	PGHH
15	Siemens	SIEMENS
16	3M India	3MINDIA
17	Cummins India	CUMMINSIND
18	GlaxoSmithKline Pharmaceuticals	GLAXO
19	Pfizer India	PFIZER
20	Sanofi India	SANOFI

The above table contains a list of companies which receive FDI and now the author based on his analysis as found out the Indian company that do not receive foreign direct investment. These companies generally operate with minimal or no foreign ownership. It relies more on its domestic capital for growth and operations. These firms do not receive foreign direct investment but might receive indirect foreign institutional investment. They are not heavily influenced by the foreign direct. This companies mainly focus on local resources for innovation and market condition to drive their business. Most of the companies in the above are public sector undertaking in India which are government owned companies which place a crucial role in the industries since these companies are PSU they are mostly controlled by the state and do not receive a significant foreign direct investment the core funding and addition making remains with the government control The below table contains the list of companies which do not receive FDI.

Table 2.2

List of companies without FDI (Sourced from 2017 to 2023 NSE and company disclosures of India)

No.	Company Name	Ticker Symbol
1	Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited (BHEL)	BHEL
2	Coal India Limited	COALINDIA
3	Oil and Natural Gas Corporation (ONGC)	ONGC
4	Bharat Petroleum Corporation Limited (BPCL)	BPCL
5	GAIL (India) Limited	GAIL
6	NTPC Limited	NTPC
7	Power Grid Corporation of India Limited	POWERGRID
8	Indian Oil Corporation Limited (IOCL)	IOC
9	Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL)	SAIL
10	Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited (HPCL)	HPCL
11	Mahanagar Telephone Nigam Limited (MTNL)	MTNL
12	National Aluminium Company Limited (NALCO)	NALCO
13	Rashtriya Chemicals and Fertilizers Limited	RCFL
14	Shipping Corporation of India	SCI
15	Mazagon Dock Shipbuilders Limited	MAZDOCK
16	Cochin Shipyard Limited	COCHINSHIP
17	Garden Reach Shipbuilders & Engineers Limited	GRSE
18	Indian Railway Catering and Tourism Corporation (IRCTC)	IRCTC
19	Rail Vikas Nigam Limited (RVNL)	RVNL
20	RITES Limited	RITES

Sectoral comparison of the selected companies

This part where the author compares the selected companies and provide the detailed analysis of industries which might attract foreign direct investment that does not. By categorising company based on the FDI status we can identify the investment pattern entrance across various different sector. This classification will help us to get a better understanding on the role of foreign direct investment in the Indian corporate landscape and economic growth.

The below graph contains the companies which receives FDI and which sector are there from. The pharmaceutical and healthcare sector attracts significant FDI due to the cost of manufacturing the drugs in India because India is a cubed with skilled workforce and strong R&D capabilities similarly FMCG sector benefits from the growing middle class and the increase in urbanisation but also rise in consumers demand so foreign companies tend to be attracted towards this. Next is the automobile industry draws FDI due to the large domestic landscape and the demand for the vehicles in India and also there are many government

initiatives in this industry. The IT sector is also one of the major hub for foreign direct investment because there is skilled workforce and outsourcing potential the manufacturing industry attracts significant FDI due to the evolving consumers preference.. overall all the industries that are scalable, high and long-term growth potential continue to attract foreign direct investment

Figure 2.2 Sectoral distribution of companies with FDI (created by author)

Next the company, which does not receive FDI and the sectors from which the companies are classified below in the graph these companies often with high government control strategic importance or regulatory restrictions the energy and petroleum, mining and metals, power and utility are largely dominated by public sector undertakings in the sectors the foreign investment is limited due to the national security concerns so it is majorly owned by government Ownership. Similarly telecommunication, railways and infrastructure sectors where the regulate reframe works are strict and the government does not allow major activity of government participation. Shipping and defence are also highly regulated as they play a vital role in the national security. It is no doubt that these sectors contribute majorly to the economy, but their dependence on the domestic funding on the government is more than the foreign investment

Figure 2.3 Sectoral distribution of companies without FDI (created by author)

In conclusion the sectors such as energy, petroleum, mining, power utilities telecommunication and defence are characterised high government control and regulatory restriction which automatically limits the foreign direct investment while the sectors like FMCG manufacturing pharmaceutical and informational technology are the sector where FDI companies are more concentrated due to the growth and the economic landscape of the Indian companies.

Analysis of the collected debt

In this section of the study the author will be discussing the statistical techniques and the software which will be used for analysing the data. After careful consideration the author chose R programming language for statistical computing and data analysis. This program has been mainly chose because it's capabilities to handle large data set and also in performing complex statistical test. It also provides us with a greater visualisation techniques. The author will be categorising the data analysis process into three segments. The first one is data cleaning, exploration data analysis and regression modelling. These three steps combined with R program makes it an ideal tool for this research

2.1 Data Preparation and Cleaning

Main purpose of this section is to complete the data and prepare it for essential use and also ensure the integrity and quality of the data before analysing. In the segment incorrect data

and missing data will be identified which can mislead to incorrect results in the statistical analysis. The below figure contains the syntax for the first segment of analysis

```
##1. Data Preparation and Cleaning##
# Check for missing values
summary(dataset) # View missing values in your dataset

# Remove or handle missing values
dataset <- na.omit(dataset) # Remove rows with missing values
# Or, replace missing values with mean
dataset$column_name[is.na(dataset$column_name)] <- mean(dataset$column_name, na.rm = TRUE)

# Check for outliers using boxplot
boxplot(dataset$column_name, main = "Boxplot of Column Name")

# Z-score for outlier detection
z_scores <- scale(dataset$column_name)
outliers <- which(abs(z_scores) > 3) # Identify outliers with Z-score > 3
```

Figure 2.4 Syntax for data preparation (created by author using R)

The first set syntax is `summary()` dysfunction provides as the summary of each column in the data set? It includes key statistics like minimum, maximum, mean, median and number of missing values. This segment mainly helps us to identify the missing values across the variables. The next syntax is `na.omit()` which helps us to remove any rows with the missing value in any column this method can significantly reduce the missing value in the data file. The next function is `boxplot()` he tells us to visually identify the distribution of the data showing us median, quartile and the potential outliers. The outliers are displayed as a discuss out of the box. It will help us to quickly identify the extreme values. The last set of code in this segment is `z_score` this helps us to standardise the data by transforming it into a form where the mean is zero and standard deviation is one. By calculating the score for each data point it helps us to identify the outliers when the score is greater than three. These points are more than three standard deviation away from the main then they are considered as an extreme outline.

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

EDA helps to understand the structure of the data its distribution and relationship with the other variable. This step will help to guide the choice of statistic method and which regression model will suit the data set here the author will be checking the normality of the data set and also developing a correlational matrix. Before proceeding with the regression analysis it is always essential to explore understanding data said this part of the study will help to check the data distribution, normality, correlation, coherence of the data. This step will ensure that the

data meets its statistical assumption and help us modify the potential skewness come outliers and multicollinearity the syntax for this part of the analysis is given below.

```
##2. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)##
# 1. Checking Data Distribution (Histogram & Density Plot)
hist(dataset$variable, col = "lightblue", main = "Histogram of Variable", breaks = 30)
plot(density(dataset$variable), col = "red", main = "Density Plot of Variable")

# 2. Normality Check using Shapiro-Wilk Test
shapiro.test(dataset$variable)

# 3. Normality Check using QQ Plot
qqnorm(dataset$variable, main = "QQ Plot of Variable")
qqline(dataset$variable, col = "red")

# 4. Correlation Analysis
cor_matrix <- cor(dataset, use = "complete.obs")
print(cor_matrix)

# 5. Coherence Check using Heatmap
heatmap(cor_matrix, col = heat.colors(10), main = "Correlation Heatmap")
```

Figure 2.5 Syntax for Exploratory data analysis (created by author using R)

In order to understand the distribution of the variables it is always crucial whether the data transformation is needed or not with the help of `hist()` it provides us a frequency distribution of the values which will help to identify the underlying patterns such as cuteness or multimodal distribution. Additionally, with the help of `Density()` it gives a smoother representation of the variables probability distribution if the program appears to be a bell shaped figure then the data is normally distributed.. the next part is to check whether the data and variables are normally distributed with the help of `shapiro.test()` which is a statistical test if the P value is less than 0.05 it suggests that the data is not normally distributed and it might need transformation.

Next is a visual analysis used to check the normality of the data set. The function `qqnorm()` compare the quartiles of the data against theoretical normal distribution if the point lies with the and along the diagonal line the data is approximately normal but if the line deviate then the data is not normally distributed. The next is correlation analysis which helps us to measure the strength and the direction of the relationship between two variables. The values of the correlation matrix is close to +1 or -1 indicate the strength of the relationship while values near zero suggest a weak or no correlation. A very high correlation between the independent areas might indicate multicollinearity so this test is one of the important test which will be carried out in this research. The last part is a heat map visualisation which represents the correlation matrix. This will be much easier to detect the strong correlation variables. The

darker colour indicates higher correlation which might also suggest that there is a high multicollinearity. The transforming of the variable is suggested or dropping the variable is also suggested in the regression analysis.

Regression Assumptions and Diagnostics

Before running the regression models, the author is to validate the underlying assumption of this model such as linearity, independence, homoscedasticity and multicollinearity. This diagnostics will help us that regression cells are reliable and interpretable.

```
##3. Regression Assumptions and Diagnostics##
# Check for multicollinearity using VIF
library(car)
vif(lm(dependent_variable ~ independent_variables, data = dataset))

# Scatterplot for linearity check
plot(dataset$independent_variable, dataset$dependent_variable, main = "Independent Variable vs Dependent Variable",
      xlab = "Independent Variable", ylab = "Dependent Variable")

# Residual Plot for homoscedasticity check
model <- lm(dependent_variable ~ independent_variables, data = dataset)
plot(model, which = 1) # Plot residuals vs fitted values
```

Figure 2.6 Syntax for regression assumptions (created by author using R)

The first function is to check the multicollinearity using `vif()` this helps us to measure how much there is a variance of the coefficient is inflated due to the multicollinearity in simple words the coalition between the independent variables. If it is a that is greater than 10 it suggests there is a significant multicollinearity in the model which can usually destroy the result if the multicollinearity is identified it is suggested to remove or combine the variables into interaction terms. The next is scatter pot for linearity check scatter pot will help us visualise the relationship between independent variable independent variable for a rear regression. There should be a linear relationship between the independent independent variable. If the relationship is non-linear the author is set to apply a transformation or considering choosing a different regression model.. the last step is building a residual plot for homoscedasticity, in this the assumption is that the variance with the residual is constant across different levels of the independent variable. In a well fitted model the rest should always be scattered around zero funnel shaped patten or clustering points suggest heteroscedasticity, which violet this assumption. If the heteroscedasticity is found in the data, we need to transfer the dependent variable or use other robust standard errors.

2.2 Regression model

In this part of the research, we will be evaluating and selecting the regression models which is a statistical tool used to analyse the relationship between the dependent and the independent variable. In the case of this study it helps us to assess how different financial indicators influence the key outcomes of market valuation. In the study enterprise value will be used as a dependent variable representing the market evaluation of the company while the other financial ratios and FDI status will be considered as our independent variable. The main objective of the studies to assess whether the companies with foreign direct investment exhibits higher market evaluation when compared to the companies which does not receive FDI.

Market valuation

The main reason why enterprise value was chosen as a key measure to assess the market valuation because it provides a deeper and accurate representation of the company total worth it takes into account both equity and debt which is more reliable than the market capitalisation. It also helps for a better comparison across company as the study includes multiple company with level of debt profitability and efficiency. And it also captures the influence of FDI more effectively in terms of increasing the market cap reducing the debt levels of the company and also announcing the operational efficiency. By capturing all these multiple effects enterprise value was chosen to represent the market valuation of the company in this research.

For the purpose of this study to regression model will be used the basic financial performance model and investment perception model where both model will focus on evaluating the impact of FDI on the market evaluation in a different perspectives capturing companies, performance and investors decision-making.

$$EV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ROE + \beta_2 D/E + \beta_3 CR + \beta_4 ATR + \beta_5 FDI_STATUS \quad (2.9)$$

Return on equity $\beta_1 ROE$: this helps to measure the profitability relative to the shareholders equity. We can also assess if the FDI inflow improves the financial efficiency of the company.

Debt to equity $\beta_2 D/E$: this indicates financial privilege of the companies if the companies leveraged more by debt or by equity FDI contribute to the capital structure while it can have an indirect impact on the enterprise value

Current ratio $\beta_3 CR$: it measures the short-term liquidity of the company and FDI helps to improve the working capital management of a company

Asset turnover ratio $\beta_4 ATR$: it reflects the operational efficiency of the company in generating revenue from its assets. FDI can also enhance the financial operation and efficiency.

FDI status $\beta_5 FDI_STATUS$: it is a binary variable 1 is for firms with FDI and 0 is for firms without FDI. It provides a direct evidence on the influence of foreign direct investment on the financial performance.

This model primarily focused on the operation and the financial efficiency perspective. It helps to determine whether financial ratios combined with FDI persons can announce the enterprise value of a company.. if the model shows a strong and positive relationship between enterprise value and the financial indicators it's such as that the firm is performing better with the infuse of foreign direct investment and the investors does sees it as an opportunity to invest in the company.

Investment perception model

The second model refers to the model that the investment perspective was taken into account. This model takes a different approach by also incorporating variables which influence the start sentiment and the market prescription. The regression equation is given below.

$$EV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ROA + \beta_2 PTE + \beta_3 PTB + \beta_4 QR + \beta_5 FDI_STATUS \quad (2.10)$$

Return on asset $\beta_1 ROA$: it reflects the company profitability relative to its total assets in investors often perceive firms with higher ROA because it could be efficiently managed. The FDI inflow can improve the asset utilization within the company.

Price to earnings ratio $\beta_2 PTE$: this is a key market-based matrix which represents how much investors are willing to pay for the company's earnings. From the literature review the author has found out that FDI can increase the price to earnings ratio of the company.

Price to book ratio $\beta_3 PTB$: he helps to measure the market valuation of the company in relative to its book value higher the price to book ratio suggest investors a company having a strong growth potential

Quick ratio $\beta_4 QR$: it is a liquidity metric which excludes inventory giving a clean picture of the short-term financial health of the company where FDI can increase the cash flow into the company thus by increasing the quick ratio

FDI status $\beta_5 FDI_STATUS$: this is similar to the first model where it is a binary variable which helps us to examine if the company with FDI performs better or not

3 Empirical part of the research

In this part of the research, the author will be analysing all collected data through predefined analysis method. The process of analysis which will be followed by the author is explained in the research methodology part of the study. The empirical part aims to evaluate relationship between foreign direct investment and the market valuation of the Indian listed companies. This section will provide focus on the analysis by testing the hypothesis outlining the previous section and also by interpreting the results. To begin with the author collected data which will be used to this research. The collected data comprises of financial performance indicator from the selected group of companies which are explained in the previous part of the study. The companies were selected based upon the significant involvement in foreign direct investment and the time period of the analysis pan across seven years from 2017 to 2024. All the collected data was stored in a separate Excel file. Later these files were uploaded into R program for further analysis. They collected data of a separated into two data assets which was companies with FDI and flow and companies without FD inflow which helped the author for comparative analysis variables in the data set included both continuous financial ratios and categorical data which indicating the presence and absence of FDI

The beginning it's before going on with the regression analysis and testing a hypothesis. It is always essential to understand the descriptive statistics of the data. This includes calculating measures such as mean, median, standard deviation also skewness of the variable. This part will help to understand the distribution of the spread of data which is crucial. Once done with descriptive statistics next step will be the testing of hypothesis which was formulated earlier section of the research. Based on the methodology. The research hypothesis will focus on the relationship of FDI flow against the market evaluation of Indian listed firm which is represented by the enterprise value. To test the hypothesis multi recreation analysis will be contacted with the collected financial variables.

Once the regression model are ready to run, it's always essential to evaluate the fit and the assumption behind this model. To understand this technique called multicollinearity check normality test and other model criteria such as AIC and BIC to compare the relativeness of the model. Finally, the results of the regression model will be analyse and discussed which helps us to identify the impact of foreign direct investment on the market evaluation of the firm and also analyse if there are any other anomalous and outline in the data will also be addressed. Additionally this section will compare the performance between two groups with them without

FDI to highlight the differences between them. The below figure is the flow chart of the authors plan for the empirical part

Figure 3.1 Structure of empirical analysis (created by author)

Descriptive statistics analysis

For companies with FDI highlights a dives financial landscape enterprise value is the moderate range from 9.81 to 12.53 reflecting a relatively high variation in the market capitalisation of the company. This indicates that the companies with FDI our spread across various sizes and various performance level with large firms generally having a higher market valuation. The return on equity ROE for these companies show a considerable variation with some achieving high returns while others are performing more modestly resulting in a positively skewed distribution. In terms of the debt to equity ratio is quite low for these firms which range is from 0.01 to 0.07 suggesting a conservative approaches of borrowing and less reliance on the

debt finance. This alliance with the companies healthy liquidity as reflected in the current ratio CR and quick ratio QR both of this indicates that the companies are well positioned to meet at short-term obligations. The asset turnover ratio AT suggest the moderate efficiency in the company utilising it are said to generate revenue while the return on asset ROA reveals abroad range of performance indicating some firms might be more effective when compared to others. The price to earnings and price to book ratios are relatively high which indicates the universe stars tend to value. These firms are very positively but some of these firms stand out as they have highest and stronger market valuation in relation to their earnings and book value. Overall, the companies with FDI demonstrate a healthier financial profile. The descriptive statistics of these companies can be seen below in the figure.

```
> describe(WFDI_with[, c("EV", "ROE", "DTE", "CR", "AT", "ROA", "PTE", "PTB", "QR")])
  vars  n mean  sd median trimmed  mad  min   max range skew kurtosis  se
EV    1 140 11.53 0.41 11.43 11.49 0.32 10.97 12.42 1.45 0.85 -0.22 0.03
ROE   2 140 29.66 18.39 22.75 26.93 12.54 11.47 69.71 58.24 1.11 0.01 1.55
DTE   3 140 0.02 0.02 0.01 0.02 0.01 0.00 0.07 0.07 1.08 -0.20 0.00
CR    4 140 2.15 0.80 2.03 2.09 0.77 0.96 3.89 2.93 0.57 -0.47 0.07
AT    5 140 1.16 0.42 1.05 1.13 0.40 0.52 2.13 1.61 0.63 -0.48 0.04
ROA   6 140 17.18 9.18 15.26 16.45 8.31 3.00 37.67 34.67 0.64 -0.47 0.78
PTE   7 140 53.82 24.52 51.11 53.01 26.03 15.50 103.63 88.14 0.26 -0.93 2.07
PTB   8 140 14.27 10.52 10.52 12.52 7.62 4.22 38.34 34.12 1.25 0.44 0.89
QR    9 140 1.70 0.76 1.58 1.62 0.78 0.68 3.46 2.77 0.78 -0.12 0.06
```

Figure 3.2 Descriptive statistics of companies with FDI (created by author)

Next the descriptive statistics analysis for the companies without FDI it reveals a different set of characteristics. The enterprise value EV shows a narrow range that companies with FDI reflecting a smaller market cap across these firms. The return on equity ROE in this group is also quiet variable with a few companies show higher returns but major majority of the company are moderate performance. The debt to equity ratio for the companies without FDI is significantly higher which indicates that the greater reliance on debt financing. Supporting this the further evidence suggest more aggressive capital structure. The liquidity is somewhat weak compare to the companies with FDI with both current ratio and quick ratio being lower. This signals that there might be challenges in managing the company short-term obligations. The asset turnover ratio is also lower in this companies because they might not be utilising the assets as effectively as the companies with FDI to generate revenue.. the return on asset for this group it shows a wide range with some performing very poor in asset utilisation. Both of the evaluation ratios of market tries to earnings and tries to book a relatively lower indicating that this companies are not highly valued compared to the FDI counterparts. Overall, the companies

FDI appears to have a greater financial challenges with higher debt levels. The below figure represents the descriptive statistics of the companies without FDI.

```
> describe(WFDI_without[, c("EV", "ROE", "DTE", "CR", "AT", "ROA", "PTE", "PTB", "QR")])
  vars  n mean  sd median trimmed mad  min  max range skew kurtosis  se
EV    1 140 11.45 0.81 11.67 11.51 1.02  9.81 12.53  2.72 -0.44  -0.89 0.07
ROE   2 140 15.56 10.40 15.28 14.85 8.81  0.00 36.88 36.88  0.46  -0.38 0.88
DTE   3 140  0.55  0.61  0.34  0.46 0.49  0.00  2.22  2.22  0.99   0.00 0.05
CR    4 140  1.16  0.48  1.02  1.13 0.50  0.55  2.05  1.50  0.46  -1.20 0.04
AT    5 140  0.68  0.48  0.53  0.62 0.39  0.18  1.68  1.50  0.95  -0.30 0.04
ROA   6 140  5.38  4.61  5.77  5.49 4.68 -5.24 13.88 19.12 -0.27  -0.03 0.39
PTE   7 140 10.79  9.13  8.03  9.64 6.03  0.00 30.71 30.71  1.02   0.13 0.77
PTB   8 140  1.39  1.03  1.15  1.29 0.81  0.00  3.60  3.60  0.79  -0.11 0.09
QR    9 140  0.90  0.57  0.69  0.85 0.50  0.19  2.26  2.08  0.69  -0.66 0.05
```

Figure 3.3 Descriptive statistics of companies with FDI (created by author using R)

When comparing both of the companies data set several key differences emerge highlighting the impact on FDI the financial performance and the market perception. Companies with FDI generally exhibits a stronger financial performance and also with a lower that equity ratio suggest that it has a better financial performance. It might be due to the inflow of foreign capital that the company is not too reliant on debt financing. In the contrast the companies without FDI tend to have a higher debt levels which may expose them to greater financial risk. This might be due to the reason that most of the companies are government owned and this companies leverage their power to get launch for managing their daily operations. Liquidity measures such as current ratio and quick ratio are more favourable with the companies with FDI suggesting that they are accused well to meet any short-term financial obligations on the other and the companies without FDI shows a weaker liquidity which could potentially cause issue in the cash flow of managing the working capital. Next is the turnover ratio suggesting that the assets are more efficiently utilised with the companies with FDI in contrast a lower efficiency was observed in the companies without FDI. It might face challenges in the management. Furthermore, the market valuation as reflected in the price to earnings and the price to book ratios are significantly higher in the companies with FDI. This indicates as the investors receive these firms having a higher growth potential. Overall in the beginning stages of this analysis the financial profile of companies with FDI appears to have a stronger better liquid lower leverage and higher market valuation highlighting that FDI can bring advantage to a company. The below figure is the main comparison of companies with and without FDI of the financial ratios

Figure 3.4 Mean comparison of companies (created by author using R)

When comparing the mean of these companies within without FDI, there is a significant difference which emerges from the data. The enterprise value for the companies with FDI is slightly higher when compared to the companies without FDI. This indicates that on average companies with FDI have marginally larger market valuation. The return on equity ROE also signifies a notable differences the companies with FDI having higher mean of 29.66 compared to companies without FDI of 15.56 this suggests that the firm generate much higher returns for their shareholders. The case of debt to equity ratio it shows as a contrast while the companies with FDI have a very low 0.02 compared to the company without FDI at 0.05 the indicates that companies without FDI tend to rely more on debt financing compared to their equ while the companies with FDI maintain a more conservative capital structure. In terms of liquidity current ratio is higher for the companies with FDI with the main value of 2.15 compared to the companies without FDI at the mean value of 1.16 it signals that the companies a better potion to meet the short term liability. Written on asset is notably higher for the companies with MTI at the mean value of 17.18 and companies without FDI at the value of 5.38 indicating a large distinction between them that the companies with FDI as utilising the assets better. Price to earnings ratio on the price to book ratio shows the companies with FDI have a higher mean to compare when with the companies without FDI this suggests that the stronger investor sentiment it's towards the companies with FDI and the investor see overall growth potential.

Figure 3.5 Mean distribution of EV (created by author using R)

Analysing the central tendency of the enterprise value with the help of violin plot it provides us with the detailed visualisation and distribution across the two groups. The median for the companies with FDI is located at a higher point of scale around 11.49. This suggests that typically the enterprise value of the firm with FDI is concentrated at the higher level. On the other hand, the median for the companies without FDI is slightly lower. With the companies with FDI the violin plot relatively narrow at top and bottom with the wider bulge in the middle. This suggests that the concentration of enterprise value is around the centre. But for the companies without FDI, the enterprise value in the violin plot is wider and more uniform. It shows a slight and narrowing at bottom. But less pronounced than the other plot. The shape suggests that the companies with FDI are more concentrated around the central value. This indicates that the values are more consistent. But the companies without FDI more uniform shapes suggest wider spread of enterprise value indicating that the companies without FDI enterprise value is variable and less predictable.

Process of identification of outlier

Outliers are the data points which significantly differ from the overall pattern of the data set. Outliers can arise due to measurement error, data entry or the natural variations in the company financials. Identifying these outliers is one of the crucial steps because it can disrupt the financial analysis. One of the most effective methods which can be used to detect outliers are the box plot, which provides us with a visual representation of the distribution of the data.

It includes median, interquartile range and extreme values. Below figure represents box plot for outline reduction with the companies with FDI.

Figure 3.6 Outlier identification of FDI dataset (created by author using R)

The above figure contains the box plot images for companies with FDI power in the key financial ratios to start with the enterprise value indicate some outliers beyond the upper whisker. It suggests that a few companies might have significantly higher enterprise value compared to the rest but the distribution of appears to be relatively symmetric with the main position near the centre of the box. Debt to equity ratio shows a considerable number of outliers which are spread throughout the upper whisker suggesting that few companies have exponent higher leverage compared to others while the majority are in the lower debt levels. Current ratio revealed several outliers in the upper whisker. But from the image we can see that of the companies are within the reasonable range. I said turnover is relatively uniform with just one outlier present. Price to book and price to earnings ratio indicates a large number of outlier on the IR hand suggesting the company have significant higher evaluation that some companies are overvalued more than others. Quick ratio also displayed multiple outliers particularly on the iron end which means the company hold unusual large portion of liquid asset. Below image contains the box plot for outline identification the companies without FDI

Figure 3.7 Outlier identification of without FDI dataset (created by author using R)

The enterprise value appears to have a lower median compared to the companies with FDI. It shows the overall normal distribution of the data by the median is the higher level. Debt to equity ratio for the companies without FDI show wider spread done with companies with FDI notably there are extreme values in the upper end indicating some companies my reliance on debt financing. Current ratio suggest that they might have a lower median with a vehicle liquidity position when compared to the firms with FDI however the few of the firms have higher current ratio value. The price to book and price to earnings ratio displays a greater range of outliers suggesting the variability in the market situation. This indicates that the non-FDI companies can experience high price speculations. Quick ratio are wider spread than FDI companies with some extreme outliers followed on by the return on asset and return on equity highlights a notable number of outliers particularly in the higher end.

Winsorization: Managing Outliers in Financial Data

Winsorization is a technique which is statistically used to limit the extreme values of outliers within a data set and replacing these outliers with a specific percentile value instead of removing the entire outliers. Entirely this method helps to adjust the extreme values to 5th and the 95th percentile. Or any specific threshold which helps to reduce the influence with preventing the overall distribution of the data. Unlike removing the data points this method helps us to preserve the data by adjusting the extreme values. Financial ratios often contain extreme values due to market volatility so this method and shows that extreme cases do not affect the conclusion. The below figure contains the syntax which is used for this method.

```

# Winsorize EV for companies with FDI
lower_limit_EV <- quantile(WFDI_with$EV, 0.05, na.rm = TRUE) # 5st percentile
upper_limit_EV <- quantile(WFDI_with$EV, 0.95, na.rm = TRUE) # 95th percentile
WFDI_with$EV <- pmin(pmax(WFDI_with$EV, lower_limit_EV), upper_limit_EV)
boxplot(WFDI_with$EV)

# Winsorize EV for companies without FDI
lower_limit_EV <- quantile(WFDI_without$EV, 0.05, na.rm = TRUE) # 5st percentile
upper_limit_EV <- quantile(WFDI_without$EV, 0.95, na.rm = TRUE) # 95th percentile
WFDI_without$EV <- pmin(pmax(WFDI_without$EV, lower_limit_EV), upper_limit_EV)
boxplot(WFDI_without$EV)

```

Figure 3.8 Process of winsorizing outlier (created by author using R)

The code applies Winsorization function to enterprise values for the both companies with and without FDI. First, the 5th and the 95th level ardia slow and upper limits respectively which ensures that only the extreme values of 5% is suggested rather than to be removed. Those values above 95% are capped at 95%. This process is performed for both data sets and also for all other ratios from which the outliers where identified. This test was performed on all the data said to maintain consistency.

Figure 3.9 Dataset after winsorizing Outlier (created by author using R)

The Winsorization techniques has been applied on enterprise value and quick ratio for the companies with and without FDI and also all other ratios which had outliers to minimise the impact of extreme values. This shows that the financial measures are more stable and also less influenced by extreme variations. While only EV and QR as shown as example the process has been applied to all the variables with outliers.

Correlation analysis with the use of heat maps

Correlation analysis is one of the crucial techniques which is used to measure the strength and the direction of the relationship between financial variables within a data set in the research. It is important to understand this relationship. It also helps us to understand how these factors such as profitability, liquidity, leverage and market evaluation influence each other. A strong correlation between these variables can potentially predict a positive relationship while a weak correlation suggests that there is little to know association. To visualise the relationship effectively the correlation heat map uses a different method. Instead of the traditional number matrix, this map provides us with a clear colour-coded representation of the correlation which makes it easy to identify the significant relationship and identify the patterns with a glance. This approach is particularly useful in a big data set like this research; it helps us to simplify the complex relationship within the variables. The below figure contains the heat map of correlation analysis of companies with FDI.

Figure 3.10 Correlation relationship of companies with FDI (created by author using R)

The above correlation heat map highlights the most significant relationship amongst the financial variables. Enterprise value shows a positive correlation with profitability indicators like return on equity price to book ratio suggesting that the firms with higher valuation and tend to have better profitability metrics. Conversely enterprise value exhibits a notable negative

correlation with liquidity measures like current ratio and quick ratio. This indicates that the company with a higher valuation tends to maintain a lower liquidity level. ROE and RO highly positive correlation enforcing the connection between the profitability and the operational efficiency of this ratios. The heat ball reveals a strong negative correlation among the asset turnover ratio and the liquidity ratios implies the firms prioritising efficiency might hold lower liquid reserves. That equity ratio appear to have relatively weaker connection with other variables. Suggesting that the debt levels does not pay a significant influence in the market valuation. Up Next is the correlation heat map of companies without FDI.

Figure 3.11 Correlation relationship of companies without FDI (created by author using R)

The above figure is the correlational heat map of the companies without FDI. Enterprise value shows the positive high correlation with debt to equity ratio and asset turnover ratio. This indicates that more valuable companies often neutralise the debt efficiently and also generate more revenue from their assets. And also a mild correlation with profitability ratios like ROE, ROA suggest us that companies with greater evaluation also have better profitability. The enterprise value also has a negative correlation between liquid measures like current ratio and quick ratio. The liquid ratios are positively correlated with ROA and ROE. It is because the companies with strong liquidity can also manage strong term obligations effectively and also better profitability. While it's negatively correlated with debt equity ratio and also as a turnover

ratio mainly it's suggest that the firms with higher liquidity tend to use less debt and focus less on maximising asset turnover they rely on so much debt.

3.1 Regression model analysis

In this part of the research, the author aims to build a regression model to assess the impact of foreign direct investment on the market valuation of Indian companies. The primary focus of the analysis is to understand how foreign directive investment influence the enterprise value of the firm to particularly distinguish between the companies that receive safety and which does not receive FDI. The author will incorporate other financial indicators as a independent variable within the model. Alongside a dummy variable was created in order to represent FDI status where 0 signifies companies without FDI and 1 signifies companies with FDI. The below figure contains the results of our initial multiple regression model

```
> model <- lm(EV ~ ROE + DTE + CR + AT + FDI_Status, data = combined_data)
> # Print the summary of the model
> summary(model)
```

Call:

```
lm(formula = EV ~ ROE + DTE + CR + AT + FDI_Status, data = combined_data)
```

Residuals:

```
      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.24731 -0.34925 -0.01414  0.37192  1.33008
```

Coefficients:

```
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept) 11.1006231  0.1112939  99.742 < 2e-16 ***
ROE          0.0002812  0.0026629   0.106  0.91599
DTE          0.6221989  0.0782553   7.951 4.87e-14 ***
CR          -0.1755356  0.0515506  -3.405  0.00076 ***
AT           0.3009143  0.0925659   3.251  0.00129 **
FDI_Status   0.4399321  0.1005409   4.376 1.72e-05 ***
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 0.5267 on 274 degrees of freedom
```

```
Multiple R-squared:  0.3469,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.335
```

```
F-statistic: 29.11 on 5 and 274 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

Figure 3.12 Regression results of market valuation model (created by author using R)

The above regression model Is aim to study the impact of foreign direct investment on the market evaluation of the company. The model is built with the enterprise value that is EV

as the dependent variable and the independent variables include Return on Equity (ROE), Debt-to-Equity (DTE), Current Ratio (CR), Asset Turnover (AT), and FDI_Status, where FDI_Status is a binary variable representing whether a company has received FDI (1) or not (0). The model 6 to explore on how these financial metrics influence the market evaluation of the company with the focus on whether FDI as a significant influence. From the above results we can see that ROE is not significantly impacting the enterprise value with the P value of 0.916. Next the debt to equity ratio as a positive relationship with the enterprise value with the coefficient of 0.622 and with a very low ($p < 0.001$), suggest that the firms with higher leverage tend to have also higher valuation. In contrast the current ratio exhibits a negative correlation with enterprise value with the coefficient of -0.175 and a P value of 0.00076 suggest that the companies with the higher liquidity attempts to have lower evaluation. Ratio is positively correlated with the enterprise value with the coefficient of 0.3009 and a P value of 0.00129 suggesting that more efficient companies in utilising the assets are valued higher. The main and the important thing is FDI status it shows the significantly positive impact on enterprise value with the coefficient of 0.4399 and with the P value of $1.72e-05$ suggesting that the companies with FDI inflow are value hired in the market this keep findings of the model is indirectly addressing the research question. The overall model explains about 34.7% of variability in the enterprise value. And with a F statistic of 29.11 ($p < 2.2e-16$) this indicating that the independent variable together predict significantly the enterprise value of the firm.

The coefficient value of 0.4399 for every day status signifies that companies with FDI tend to have a higher enterprise value compared to those without FDI additionally all the variables in the models I've also contributed alongside FDI status as they result further enforces the positive impact of FDI on the company market performance the statistical significance also helps to confirm the relationship is not due to random chance it underscores the positive effect of foreign direct investment.

Even though the initial model serves as a foundational step in order to analyse the impact of FDI on enterprise value. Other model will also be created to get a valuable insight into the relationship. The next phase of analysis will focus on identifying the influential points which might affect the result.

```

# Calculate Cook's Distance
cooks_distance <- cooks.distance(model)

# Find which points are influential (typically points with Cook's Distance > 4/n)
n <- length(cooks_distance)
influential_points <- which(cooks_distance > (4 / n))

# Print the indices of the influential points
influential_points

# Plot Cook's Distance to visualize influential points
plot(cooks_distance, type = "h", main = "Cook's Distance", ylab = "Cook's Distance")
abline(h = 4 / n, col = "red", lty = 2) # Adding a threshold line

```

Figure 3.13 Calculation of cook's distance point (created by author using R)

Identifying the influential points is one of the crucial steps to ensure that the results are not affected by extreme values even though with the help of box plot and winsorization the outliers were eliminated but still some might influence the model. One of the common method which is used to detect these points is by calculating Cook's distance. Statistical method is used to measure and identify the influential point in a regression analysis. The statistics tool calculates for each observation the data set and measure the change in the regression fitted values. The below figure contains the influential point which was identified using. Cook's distance statistic tool.

Figure 3.14 Result of cook's distance point (created by author using R)

From the above figure, the author created to identify the cook distant points which were found out influential with the help of the statistical test. The next step in the analysis is to create a regression model with the same variables but removing the influential points. The influential points significantly impact the models estimates and can also distort the result which leads to misleading conclusions. By eliminating this outliers. The author can create more robust and reliable model which better represents the relationship between the variables. This steps ensure that this model will not overlay sensitive to outliers and provide more accurate and also in-depth description of the underlying relationship. The below figure contains the regression model without influential points. This adjustment improve the model robust and also ensure that the outliers is not affecting the results. The models intercept is at 11.29 which means when all of the independent variables are zero they expect an enterprise value will be at 11.29 on a logarithmic scale.

```
> summary(model_without_influential_points)

Call:
lm(formula = EV ~ ROE + DTE + CR + AT + FDI_Status, data = combined_data[-c(91,
  154, 209, 227, 239, 240, 242, 244, 253, 256, 257, 263), ])

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.29585 -0.32827  0.01477  0.35611  0.97028

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept) 11.2943398  0.1066244 105.926 < 2e-16 ***
ROE          0.0003079  0.0024674   0.125  0.90078
DTE          0.5900908  0.0743618   7.935 6.14e-14 ***
CR          -0.2336321  0.0476501  -4.903 1.66e-06 ***
AT           0.2327116  0.0868985   2.678  0.00788 **
FDI_Status   0.4442795  0.0917075   4.845 2.17e-06 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.4758 on 262 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.3712,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.3592
F-statistic: 30.93 on 5 and 262 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

Figure 3.15 Regression results of market valuation model without influential points (created by author using R)

In this model also the return and equity is not statistically significant and does not have a meaningful impact on the enterprise value. The debt equity ratio as a significant P value of 6.14e-14 it suggests a very strong positive relationship within this variable. current ratio is also

statistically significant but with the negative coefficient he suggests that there is a negative relationship between liquidity and enterprise value. The asset turnover as a positive coefficient of 0.232 and with the P value of 0.0078 indicating the companies with a higher asset turnover tends to have higher enterprise value. Finally the important FDI status as a coefficient value of 0.444 and with a significant P value of $2.17e-06$ reinforcing defining from the previous model of the companies with FDI tend to perform better. The R squared value of 0.37 and adjusted as square value of 0.35 suggesting that the model explains about 37.12% of the variation in the enterprise value. And the F statistics of 30.93 with a P value ($< 2.2e-16$) which is significant indicates the model is statistically significant and at least one of the predictor is significantly related to the enterprise value.

The next step in the study is to build a model without ROE. Since ROE was found out statistically insignificant in the previous both models with a P value of 0.0078 and 0.91599 it does not contribute to the meaningful relationship between the variation in the enterprise value therefore the next logical step is to build degradation model without ROE as an independent variable keeping the adult independent variable stable. This model will build while keeping all the influential point in the data in order to understand that the full scope of this model because the addition to retain the influential points in this model is also based on understanding that the presence might still provide the valuable insights even if they have an impact on the large model. While this model will not be the most refined model, it provides us with the reasonable analysis and balancing the inclusion of data and the exclusion of non-significant variable.

```
> model_without_ROE <- lm(EV ~ DTE + CR + AT + FDI_Status, data = combined_data)
> summary(model_without_ROE)
```

Call:

```
lm(formula = EV ~ DTE + CR + AT + FDI_Status, data = combined_data)
```

Residuals:

```
      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.24804 -0.34766 -0.01123  0.37377  1.33573
```

Coefficients:

```
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  11.10231    0.10994  100.985 < 2e-16 ***
DTE           0.62051    0.07647   8.115 1.64e-14 ***
CR           -0.17579    0.05140  -3.420 0.000722 ***
AT            0.30662    0.07499   4.089 5.70e-05 ***
FDI_Status    0.44052    0.10021   4.396 1.58e-05 ***
```

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Residual standard error: 0.5258 on 275 degrees of freedom
```

```
Multiple R-squared:  0.3469,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.3374
```

```
F-statistic: 36.52 on 4 and 275 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

Figure 3.16 Regression results of market valuation model without ROE (created by author using R)

The above model excludes return on equity and shows the other Independent variables like that to equity, current ratio, set turnover ratio and FDI status. All the variables remains statistically significant in the prediction of enterprise value. The FDI status with the coefficient value of 0.44 with a high significant P value of 1.58e-05 indicating us that the companies with FDI might have higher market valuation it is very consistent with the findings from the previous model. Current ratio does a turnover ratio also have a significant relation with negative and positive coefficient with the enterprise value. Finally the R squared value is 0.3469 suggesting that the moral explains approximately of 34.69% the variance in the enterprise value. How about to keep a note that the exclusion of return on equity was made due to its significance. And this model provide provides a better fit by removing less useful predictor.

Model Comparison Using AIC and BIC

In order to determine the most suitable model to explain the relationship between enterprise value on the other variables. Three models were built the basic model, the model without influential points and the model without ROE know the author will be comparing their performance using AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) and BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion). This test will help to assess the fit of each model while comparing and considering

the models complexity generally the lower AIC and BIC values suggest a better fitting model. AIC penalising the model complexity and BIC imposing an even stronger penalty for the additional parameters with the help of this model is the evaluation we can select the most optimal model for explaining the market evaluation of the companies based on FDI and other influencing variables.

Figure 3.17 Model Comparison Using AIC and BIC values (created by author using R)

Based upon the AIC and the BIC value model two that is the model without the influential points emerge as the best model amongst the three it has the lowest AIC of 370.39 and BIC off 395.53 indicating it the best amongst the three in the terms of model complexity and the fit. And also effectively capturing the relationship between the variables without overfitting in comparison with the model one and model three without ROE have higher values suggesting that they are less effective. From this test the author found out that the model two is the most optimal model asset balance between capturing the data pattern and minimising unnecessary complexity.

Multicollinearity and Heteroscedasticity Diagnostics

We are finalised the regression model it is essential to evaluate the underlying assumptions within the model. The two common steps used for this purpose Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and the Breusch-Pagan (BP) test. The VIF test is used to assess the multicollinearity among the independent variable in the model. This occur when two or more predicts are highly correlated. Next the BP test is used to detect the heteroscedasticity within

the model it refers to the time where the variance of the year term is not constant across all level of independent variable. This can lead to significant and efficiency estimates by performing these to test the author can assure that the regression model meets the key assumption.

```
> print(bp_test)
```

```
studentized Breusch-Pagan test
```

```
data: model_without_influential_points
BP = 41.16, df = 5, p-value = 8.709e-08
```

```
> vif(model_without_influential_points)
```

	ROE	DTE	CR	AT	FDI_Status
	2.001112	1.593842	1.801093	2.219708	2.485372

Figure 3.18 Results of Multicollinearity and Heteroscedasticity Diagnostics (created by author using R)

The above figure Contains the results of BP test and VIF test. To begin with the BP test for heteroscedasticity in the model the BP statistics were 41.16 with DF = 5 and a P value of 8.709e-08 that there is a significant of heteroscedasticity in this model. This means that the result do not have a constant variance. But with the interpretation of the VIF test all the values are below 10 suggesting that the multicollinearity is not a major consent in the model and the predicts are not highly correlated with each other meaning the coefficient of the model are relatively stable and reliable. The next step is in order to face the models heteroscedasticity the use of robust error technique used to be used.

The robust standard error is a statistical technique which is used to adjust the standards of the regression coefficient in the account for atrocity within the data set. To explain more detail in the normal regression model it is assumed that the variance of the error terms is constant across all observation but it is not always in this pattern to adjust for the heteroscedasticity by calculating the standard error of the coefficient this is more reliable in the presence of unequal variance.

```

> robust_se <- sqrt(diag(vcovHC(model_without_influential_points, type = "HC1")))
> # Perform robust t-tests
> robust_results <- coefTest(model_without_influential_points, vcov = vcovHC(model_without_influential_points, type = "HC1"))
> print(robust_results)

```

t test of coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	11.29433982	0.11698961	96.5414	< 2.2e-16 ***
ROE	0.00030791	0.00232239	0.1326	0.894626
DTE	0.59009076	0.06582550	8.9645	< 2.2e-16 ***
CR	-0.23363210	0.04391355	-5.3203	2.225e-07 ***
AT	0.23271158	0.07922735	2.9373	0.003606 **
FDI_Status	0.44427946	0.09411378	4.7207	3.832e-06 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Figure 3.19 Regression results of RSE market valuation model (created by author using R)

The table contains the result of robust test for the regression model without influential points. As seen from the other models ROE is not statistically significant and does not have a meaningful impact but all the other variables like that to equity, current ratio asset turnover ratio have a significant effect on the dependent variable. This model shows that the statistical significance of the variable are more accurate and assessed which compared to the earlier model that there is a presence of heteroscedasticity. Making the results of this model reliable to the real world data where the unequal variances often present.

In the next part of the study, the author will be evaluating the model assumption which is one of the crucial factors. The models which are going to be assessed at the first model, which is the basic model and the optimal model which is named as model without influential points below figure contains the image of residual vs fitted plot

Figure 3.20 Residual vs fitted plot of Regression results of market valuation model (created by author using R)

The above figure contains two graphs which shows the residual vs fitted plot, this figure helps us to evaluate if the model is good by showing how the residuals are distributed across the predicted values. The X axis is represented by the fitted values and the Y axis is represented by the worlds. Generally the rescue should be randomly scattered around zero indicating that the model is capturing the pattern in the data well without any bias in the first plot which is the basic model we observed that some residual are highly spread and it has influential points like 283, 540 the deviates significantly from the pattern. Along with this, the red line shows that it is not flat trend suggest that there is a potential violation of regression assumption like linearity and also may be homoscedasticity. When it comes to the second plot which is the plot without influential points the spread of the race is more uniform. The extreme values have been removed and it has the most stable model. The smoothing line in between is much more flatter compared to the previous one indicating the resids are mostly distributed across the middle zero this helps to increase the models reliability. With the help of this model the transformation within this model and see the validity of the regression assumption making the final model a better fit in order to assess the relationship between the impact of FDI and enterprise value.

Figure 3.21 QQ plot of Regression results of market valuation model (created by author using R)

The above figure is a normal QQ plot which helps to assess whether acids of regression model follows a normal distribution. It was one of the key assumptions for the linear regression model. In the figure the access is represented by theoretical quantities while the Y axis is represented by standardise residual. For an ideal model the point should lie along the 45° reference line indicating that the residue are normally distributed in the first plot. We can observe some deviation on the lower and the upper end particular leave the influential points like 283, 154, 263 and so on. That deviation from the line suggest that there might be presence

of outliers and other potential non-normalities. But in the second plot of model without influential points, the alignment of the line is much more improved when compared to the previous one, especially at the tail indicating a better normality spread the removal of the residual points has reduced the extreme deviation in the line leading to a more normal distributed residual pattern. This factor helps us to adjust and enhance the robustness of the model and also ensuring that it is statistically good and it helps to test our hypothesis which is more reliable from the second model.

Investment perception model

This model highlights that how investors perceive the company is based on the financial. This model explains how an investor might evaluate the company on the potential returns, risks and overall value aligning with the choice of variable like price to earnings ratio, price to book ratio, return on assets and quick ratio. This model helps to highlight not only the general market sentiment but on how investors view the financial health and market evaluation of the company based on foreign direct investment.

The results of the model are given in the below figure. It explains that the intercept which is highly significant with a very small P value suggest suggesting that the model has a very strong base. The first variable or A has a positive and a statistically significant relationship with the enterprise value in the value of 0.0451. Suggest that the investor perceives the companies are more efficient and profitable. Price to earnings ratio is not statistically significant suggesting that it does not have a strong relationship with the dependent variable that is enterprise value. This could also suggest that the investors might not prioritise PE ratio as a major determinant of the market valuation. Price to book ratio is also similar and not statistically significant indicating the less importance. Following it the quick ratio is statistically significant but as a negative relationship with enterprise value suggesting that the lower quick ratio tends to have a lower enterprise value. This might negatively impact the investors perception of a company with poor short-term liquidity. And finally the FDI status is not statistically significant with the P value of 0.55. This suggest that the presence of FDI in this case does not have a strong effect on the enterprise value of this model.

```

> model2 <- lm(EV ~ ROA + PTE + PTB+ QR + FDI_Status, data = combined_data)
> summary(model2)

Call:
lm(formula = EV ~ ROA + PTE + PTB + QR + FDI_Status, data = combined_data)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.72062 -0.38625  0.02917  0.44424  1.03215

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept) 11.611952   0.086062 134.925 < 2e-16 ***
ROA          0.017144   0.008519   2.013  0.0451 *
PTE          0.004375   0.002971   1.473  0.1420
PTB         -0.010966   0.009567  -1.146  0.2527
QR          -0.317849   0.061676  -5.154  4.9e-07 ***
FDI_Status   0.088988   0.149776   0.594  0.5529
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.6145 on 274 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.1109,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.09469
F-statistic: 6.836 on 5 and 274 DF,  p-value: 4.983e-06

```

Figure 3.22 Regression results of investment perception model (created by author using R)

But to keep a note that the difference between this model and the previous model without influential points where the FDI status was significant and in this it is not significant here. It can be explained by different set of variables were included in this model where earlier model and included return on equity ratio, current ratio, asset turnover ratio and debt to equity. This model turned out to be statistically significant of FDI status suggest that the presence of FDI have a positive impact on the market evaluation of the company. The presence of FDI is likely to be signalled by the investor confidence and access to the capital both which are the key points in the factory determining the companies market valuation.

But in the second model with the enterprise value as a dependent variable and a different set of independent variable and it turns out to be FDI status as in significant. The major difference could be the new set of financial indicators especially price to earnings and price to book ratios do not capture the same aspect of the companies performance. This variables are there to measure the market prescription of the company. The lack of significance of foreign direct investment in this model such as the effect of foreign direct investment in a different context meaning it might have a very based on order economy, sectoral and company specific factors. FDI can also be impacting enterprise through the channels which are not captured in this market oriented financial ratios such as long-term benefits and market expansion.

Confidence might be critical through FDI which influences market valuation but it is highly unlikely to be captured by the financial ratios used to the second model. Financial ratios like price to earnings and price to book primarily focus on measure bill, historical financial data and it might not fully capture the broader impact of the foreign direct investment and also the market investment sentiment and market expectations. So therefore while FDI can have a positive influence on the market evaluation, it may not be fully reflected in the financial ratios in the second model.

Conclusions and proposals

The studies main game used to examine the impact of foreign direct investment on the market valuation of publicly listed Indian companies and getting insights from both the theoretical and empirical analysis. The ground work on the foundation of the studies are financial theory is such as Modigliani and Miller's propositions and the Financial Liberalization Hypothesis, this theory helped us to_ how capital structure, market efficiency and regulatory dynamics collectively shape evaluation outcomes of foreign direct investment.

The theoretical framework established that FDI serves more than a capital inflation tool, but overall improving the companies credibility. As seen in the Modigliani and Miller's proposition especially with the tax consideration, FDI usually operates similar to debt in optimising the firms value through tax shield and by minimising the financial risks due to equity nature of foreign capital. Financial liberalisation hypothesis further supports the liberalisation of the economy with the robust financial system such as India's post 1991 reforms are more capable of leveraging foreign direct investment for advanced productivity and sustainable growth.

Literature review also provide any extensive support for the argument that FDI positively influence the market valuation buddies have shown that FDI contributes to the technological spillover, management efficiency and innovation capacity factors which ultimately answers the firm competitiveness and investors perception. The evidence which I gather gathered from the emerging markets during the literature review also I've confirmed that FDI announcement typically generate a positive market reaction suggesting in investor confidence

This research also highlighted the role of evolving an emerging regulatory framework in facilitating foreign direct investment in flow Reforms under acts like FEMA (1999), the Companies Act (2013), and the liberalized industrial policy of 1991 has created and friendly environment to involve in foreign investment. Additionally, the difference in the Indian states were found to be influenced by infrastructural development, government quality, policy initiatives and workforce skill level

The empirical part of the analysis was set out to identify the relationship between foreign direct investment and the market valuation of the Indian listed company. The analysis started with descriptive statistics of the firms with and without FDI while comparing the mean values of the selected financial ratios it was clear that the companies with foreign direct investment had a higher mean value suggesting that the companies were better performing. But with the

help of the violin plot the author found out that there could be potential outliers to identify the outliers author used box plot technique and once the outlier was confirmed the author moved on with managing the outlier with a technique called winsorization. With the help of this technique the author trimmed the outliers to the 5th and 95th percentile.

The first model the author build was to analyse the impact of foreign direct investment on the market valuation of Indian invested companies for this purpose. The author took the enterprise value as a dependent variable and independent variables where ROE, DTE, CR, AT, FDI these were all the ratios which were selected as an independent variable. The results of this model is where the adjusted R square Value of 35% and multiple R squared value of 33%. And in the model all the variables were statistically significant except Return on equity P. Value of 0.91599 which is not statistically significant. The author moved on with eliminating the influential points with the help of cook distance method. Row numbers 91, 154, 209, 227, 239, 240, 242, 244, 253, 256, 257, 263 where all identified as influential points. Once after the model was run again without the influential points the model statistics improved slightly with the adjusted R squared value of 35% but still ROE remained in significant with the P value of 0.90078. Since the ROE was not statistically significant the author has decided to remove ROE and run another model. In this model all the variables for statistically significant with the adjusted R squared value of 34%. Now for the first model the author has created three different regression model. The author wanted to find out which of the model is the best using AIC and BIC values. And with the help of this test the model without influential point scored low in the test with a AIC value of 370.39 and a BIC value of 395.53. The base model had the highest AIC value of 443.51 and highest BIC value of 468.95. And the model without ROE had a IC value of 441.52 and BIC value of 463.33. With the help of this results the author concluded that the model without the influential point is better model. Before concluding that this model was the final model which will be used for the interpretation the author conducted multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity test. the results of BP test and VIF test. To begin with the BP test for heteroscedasticity in the model the BP statistics were 41.16 with $DF = 5$ and a P value of $8.709e-08$ that there is a significant of heteroscedasticity in this model. Since the model is not homogeneous, the author moved on with robust stand error technique. This is used adjust the pattern of the variance for heteroscedasticity by calculating the standard error of the coefficient. The results of the robust error model without the influential points is similar to the model before. Only ROE is not statistically significant as seen as in the previous model with the P value of 0.894626. The FDI variable was the strongest predict with a P value of 0.0000038 signifies that it is a very strong relationship with the coefficient of 0.4442 suggest that FDI had a significant

impact on the market value of the company. So the optimal model which was used for interpretation was the RSE model without influential points.

The second model was the investment perception model. This model was used to highlight how the stars perceive the company based on their financial for the purpose of this model enterprise value was used as a dependent variable with ROA, PTE, PTB, QR and FDI value used as independent variable. The initial model came out with the results out of five variables only two of the variable was statistically significant. The models adjusted our squared value was 94%. Odd year was statistically significant with a P value of 0.0451 and with the coefficient value of 0.017, and quick ratio was also statistically significant with a P value of 0.0000007 and with the negative coefficient value of -0.3178. This model was used to analyse the investment perception with the results of this model the author concludes that this model has ratios which do not directly influence the market valuation of the company due to this FDI can have a positive influence on the market evaluation but it does not fully reflected in the financial ratios within this model.

1. What is the impact of FDI on the market valuation of selected Indian listed companies?

The study confirms that FDI has a statistical and a positive impact on the enterprise value the optimal regression model after removing the outliers and correcting for heteroscedasticity showed a positive coefficient of FDI 0.4442 and with the highest significant P value of 0.0000038 indicating that FDI directly contributes the higher market valuation

2. How does FDI influence financial performance indicators such as profitability, liquidity, and efficiency?

The analysis found mixed result some indicators like quick ratio and asset turnover where significant in explaining the valuation but ROE consistently failed to show significant and was removed in the final model. This suggests that FDI improves some aspects of the performance of the company, but it's influence might not be captured by traditional financial ratios.

3. Does the presence of FDI lead to a significant difference in the enterprise value of companies compared to those without FDI?

Yes, the comparative analysis of the firms with and without FTI revealed that companies with FDI had a higher mean enterprise value supporting this hypothesis that FDI contributes to the superior market evaluation. This was also confirmed with regression outcomes and robustness checks.

Based on the entire analysis, the author controls that the hypothesis **H1**: *Companies with FDI have a significantly higher market valuation, as measured by enterprise value, compared to companies without FDI is **accepted***

Based upon the findings of the research the proposal are given by the author to guide stakeholders and future studies on the influence of foreign direct investment on the market valuation listed companies in India

- **Future research** should explore FDI impact market valuation and also operational performance on the sector level **what** need across different sectors like pharmaceutical, FMCG, automotive, IT. By comparative analysis approach the researchers can identify high yield disectors for FDI and sector specific dynamics. Contact detailed analysis of effectiveness of the regulatory framework such as FEMA (1999), Companies Act (2013), and state-level policies. **Why** this is importance is because it can help to identify high yield sectors for FBI and uncover sector specific dynamics.
- **Government agency** or relevant institutions should consider developing a readiness index- **what** this index should include our indicate as like infrastructure quality, policy transparency and skilled labour availability and also ease of doing business. **Why** this is useful is because it would help to assess how prepared each Indian state or sector in order to attract high-quality foreign direct investment.
- **Local companies** they should adapt to international practising – **what** they need to do is align with global best practices, enhance transparency, communicate ESG goals effectively and also maintain a balanced capital structure with both debt and equity. **Why** this is important is to meet investors expectation and increase attractiveness of the FDI destination.
- **Foreign companies** or investing in in India, they have to contact a sector specific due diligence- **what** they need identify the local sector dynamics, regulatory environment and competitive in intensity before investing in high growth sectors. The companies should not only concentrate on short-term benefits but also build a long-term partnership. **Why** this matters is The foreign companies should also focus on regulatory alignment with Indian regulatory framework to ensure seamless operations and minimise entry barriers
- **Companies entering in joint venture and strategic alliance** must establish a clear government structure- **what** they should focus on includes promoting knowledge and skill transfer, aligning business culture and their values and using enterprise value

matrix to track the impact. **Why** this approach is beneficial is because it produces the gap between domestic and international teams and also ensure smooth collaboration and measurable success.

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